

Report

**First Indigenous and local knowledge
dialogue workshop**

on the

IPBES second global assessment

3-7 November, Windsor, Canada

Suggested citation

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Disclaimer

The text in section 3 represents an attempt to reflect solely the views and contributions of the participants in the dialogue. As such, it does not represent the views of IPBES or UNESCO or reflect upon their official positions.

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1 Introduction

This report summarizes the proceedings from the first Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) dialogue workshop for the second global assessment of biodiversity and ecosystem services that is being developed by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystems Services (IPBES).

The dialogue workshop was held in Windsor, Canada from 3 to 7 November 2025. It aimed to provide a platform for discussion between Indigenous Peoples and local communities and authors of the second global assessment, with a focus on key ILK concepts, themes, questions, challenges, opportunities, resources and other issues relating to the assessment.

The workshop also discussed methods for working with ILK in IPBES assessments, which contributes to ongoing efforts to review and enhance the ways that IPBES engages with ILK. That aspect of the workshop will be covered in a separate report.

This report aims to provide a written record of the parts of the dialogue workshop relevant to the second global assessment. It is intended to serve as a reference for assessment authors as they develop the assessment, as well as for dialogue participants and others interested in biodiversity and ILK, who may wish to review and contribute to this work in the future.

The report does not aim to provide a comprehensive account or to resolve all the thought-provoking discussions that took place. Instead, it offers a written record of those discussions, which are expected to continue to develop and evolve in the months and years. For this reason, the report highlights both areas of agreement and instances where participants expressed differing perspectives, to encourage further reflection and dialogue.

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The agenda and participants' list for the dialogue workshop are provided in annexes 1 and 3.

2 Background

2.1 The IPBES second global assessment

The overall objective of the second IPBES global assessment of biodiversity and ecosystem services (referred to as “the second global assessment”) is to assess progress towards achieving the goals of sustainability and living in harmony with nature. The second global assessment will strengthen the science-policy interface on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people on a range of spatial scales, from the local to the global, by providing the knowledge and the policy support tools needed for informed decision-making.

The second global assessment as a whole will implement the [IPBES approach to recognizing and working with Indigenous and local knowledge](#).

The assessment will consist of a **summary for policymakers** and **five chapters**:

1. Setting the scene
2. Different knowledge systems and the role of Indigenous Peoples and local communities
3. Status and trends
 - 3.1 Good quality of life
 - 3.2 Direct and indirect drivers
 - 3.3 Nature
 - 3.4 Nature’s contributions to people
4. Future pathways
5. Options for action

Chapter 2 is of particular relevance for work with ILK. This individual chapter will explore the diverse and plural values and world views of Indigenous Peoples and local communities all over the world, drawing out common themes, among other aims. The chapter will inform other chapters on how to weave together diverse world views, including Indigenous and local knowledge systems.

The second global assessment will be delivered in 2028.

The scoping document for the second global assessment is available [here](#).

2.2 Context for the dialogue workshop

2.2.1 IPBES and ILK

IPBES is an independent intergovernmental body established to strengthen the science-policy interface for biodiversity and ecosystem services for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, long-term human well-being and sustainable development.

Since its inception in 2012, IPBES has recognized that Indigenous Peoples and local communities possess detailed knowledge of biodiversity and ecosystem trends. In its first work programme (2014-2018), IPBES built on this recognition through deliverable 1 (c), *Procedures, approaches, and participatory processes for working with Indigenous and local knowledge systems*. The IPBES rolling work programme up to 2030 includes objective 3 (b), *Enhanced recognition of and work with Indigenous and local knowledge systems*, which aims to further this work. The IPBES conceptual framework also contains explicit recognition of diverse knowledge and value systems.

The IPBES Plenary also established a [task force on ILK systems](#) and agreed on [terms of reference](#) guiding its operations towards implementing this deliverable. IPBES' work with Indigenous Peoples and local communities and on ILK is supported by a technical support unit for ILK, hosted by UNESCO.

Key activities and deliverables of the task force and technical support unit on ILK so far include:

- Progress in the development of approaches and methodologies for working with ILK was made during previous IPBES assessments (Pollination, Pollinators and Food Production, Land Degradation and Restoration, four Regional Assessments and a Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, Sustainable Use of Wild Species, Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature, Invasive Alien Species, the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health, Transformative Change, and Business and Biodiversity);
- The development and implementation of the “[approach to recognizing and working with ILK in IPBES](#)”, which was formally approved by the Plenary at its fifth session in 2017 in decision IPBES-5/1, which sets out principles and approaches for IPBES's work with ILK;
- Development and implementation of methodological guidance for recognizing and working with ILK in IPBES, which aims to provide further detail and guidelines on how to work with ILK within the IPBES context; and
- Development and implementation of a “[participatory mechanism](#)”, a series of activities and pathways to facilitate the participation of Indigenous Peoples and local communities in IPBES assessments and other activities, which includes organizing [ILK dialogue workshops](#) for the IPBES assessments.

2.2.2 Working with ILK in the assessment process

Following the IPBES approach to ILK and as part of the participatory mechanism, three ILK dialogue workshops are held during the cycle of an IPBES assessment, as follows:

1. Discussing key ILK themes and framing of the assessment (in the first months after an assessment commences);
2. Reviewing the first draft of the chapters (during the assessment's first external review period); and
3. Reviewing the second draft of the chapters and first draft of the summary for policymakers (during the assessment's second external review period).

An online dialogue workshop also took place in 2024 to discuss the scoping report of the assessment. The report for that workshop is available [here](#).

These workshops bring together members of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, Indigenous and non-indigenous scientists, and authors of the assessment to discuss key themes relating to the assessment. They are part of a series of complementary activities for working with ILK and enhancing participation by Indigenous Peoples and local communities throughout the assessment process.

Other activities during an assessment include an online call for contributions, invitations to contributing authors and review of diverse literature and materials.

2.3 Objectives of the ILK dialogue workshop

The first ILK dialogue aims to provide a platform for discussion between participants of the workshop about potential key ILK concepts, themes, questions, challenges, opportunities, resources and other issues relating to the IPBES second global assessment. Specific aims of the dialogue include:

1. Examine the scope and key concepts of the second global assessment, and co-develop ILK-relevant themes and guiding questions to inform the assessment;
2. Identify opportunities, risks, and benefits of the assessment from the perspectives of Indigenous Peoples and local communities;
3. Building on the work on methods, further develop a series of methods and approaches for the second global assessment;
4. Develop relevant case studies rooted in ILK systems;
5. Identify key experts from Indigenous Peoples and local communities for future contributions to the assessment and related dialogue workshops; and
6. Compile ILK-based resources and information for the assessment.

2.4 Methods for the dialogue workshop

The workshop was held in-person over five days, and it first addressed methods for working with ILK in IPBES before shifting attention to the second global assessment. Throughout the workshop, strong links were made between these two discussions, and the discussions on methods directly informed those relating to the second global assessment. At the outset, time was also dedicated for participants to identify the issues they wished to explore and agree on how these should be addressed. The full agenda is presented in annex 1 of this report.

The process for the dialogue workshop included:

- Initial presentations and discussions on:
 - IPBES and its goals and methods;
 - Workshop aims, methods, and free, prior and informed consent (FPIC); and
 - The assessment, its goals and proposed methods;
- Discussions around the key ILK questions and themes for the second global assessment as a whole and for each chapter of the assessment. Participants were asked to reflect on key questions and themes and provide examples and case studies that could support work in the chapters;
- A day of community and land visits to:
 - A wetland site, plant medicine and food sovereignty garden that had been restored by Caldwell First Nation, where workshop participants participated in an Anishnaabe water ceremony; and
 - Point Pelee National Park to hear jointly from members of Caldwell First Nation and Parks Canada about the biocultural significance and history of the area; and
- Two sessions of the Indigenous and local community caucus, an informal group composed of Indigenous and local community representatives, with *ad hoc* rules of engagement, to give participants a space to discuss any questions, concerns or issues in relation to IPBES, the assessment and the workshop.

2.5 Free, prior and informed consent

The principles of Free, prior and informed consent (FPIC) are central to IPBES's engagement with Indigenous Peoples and local communities. A series of ethical principles have been developed to ensure that FPIC is followed in IPBES activities. These principles were jointly agreed upon by the participants from Indigenous Peoples and local communities and by IPBES authors during the dialogue, recognizing that participants, authors and the IPBES technical support units have

different responsibilities within the process. The principles will be followed by participants from Indigenous Peoples and local communities, the assessment authors group and the IPBES technical support units. The full agreed-upon text and the names of those agreeing to these principles are provided in annexes 2 and 3 to this report.

2.6 Benefits to Indigenous Peoples and local communities from participating in the assessment and other activities

During previous ILK workshops, participants emphasized the importance of ensuring that Indigenous Peoples and local communities derive clear and meaningful benefits from their engagement and participation in the assessment process. It was noted that IPBES does not benefit financially from its processes or products. Instead, its main outputs, such as assessment reports, summaries for policymakers, webinars and other publicly accessible materials and resources, are designed to provide free and reliable information to policymakers, decision-makers, and actors at all levels, including Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The key benefits identified for Indigenous Peoples and local communities through participation in dialogue workshops and the broader assessment process include:

- The opportunity to enhance relationships, and share experiences, examples and cases among Indigenous Peoples and local communities around the world;
- The opportunity for Indigenous Peoples and local communities to engage in dialogue with IPBES assessment authors, sharing experiences and knowledge;
- The opportunity to bring ILK, as well as the concerns and perspectives of Indigenous Peoples and local communities to the attention of policymakers and decision-makers; and
- The use of final assessments as practical tools to support Indigenous Peoples and local communities in their engagement with policymakers, decision-makers and scientists.

As part of the assessment process, an accessible summary specifically designed for Indigenous Peoples and local communities will be developed once the assessment is finalised, as well as webinars that present the findings and results to these groups.

3 Key recommendations and learning from the dialogue workshop¹

Throughout the workshop, participants engaged in discussions about various aspects of the second global assessment. This section highlights the key messages, recommendations and examples shared by Indigenous Peoples and local communities during the workshop. To preserve authenticity, the content presented here closely reflects the participant's statements and comments during the workshop, with only minor editorial adjustments for clarity.

3.1 The overall approach to the assessment

Participants shared their aspirations for the overall approach to the assessment, which included:

- The assessment could aim to go beyond simply updating the findings and analysis of the first global assessment, to instead offer a **transformative vision** that moves from biodiversity conservation towards revitalization of biocultural systems, reframing societal values and reimagining the roles of research and governance. Participants noted that ILK can provide different perspectives on the scope of the assessment and reframe its key themes and objectives.
- Given that **ILK systems, as well as the contributions, roles, and rights of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, are woven throughout the KMGBF**, the second global assessment could seek to demonstrate how to operationalize, implement, monitor and build on this framework.
- **A coherent narrative and strong collaboration across all chapters** will be crucial, particularly relating to terminology, concepts and frameworks. Authors from other chapters can be engaged to co-develop and understand the concepts and frameworks in chapter 2, through an iterative process, to ensure that chapter 2's work is coherent with other chapters. It will be important for all authors to be aware of the concepts, frameworks and methods addressed in each chapter to ensure meaningful coherence and connection across chapters. Mechanisms for this collaboration include contributing authors working as contributing authors to other chapters, or through discussions in the liaison group. Participants noted

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that while past assessments have included valuable work on Indigenous concepts and worldviews, this work has not always been sustained across all chapters. The second global assessment should aim to rectify this.

- The second global assessment represents an opportunity to **examine the interface between different knowledge systems**, including exploring and demonstrating what it means to assemble a body of evidence on ILK, and how it should be explored and analysed. This could serve as a model for other processes, such as NBSAP reports developed by governments. This could include examining conservation outcomes on the ground, rather than knowledge in the abstract. This exploration could also include an examination of the ways that confidence levels are assigned to findings in assessments.
- The assessment could include **diverse representations of knowledge**, including storytelling, videos and artworks. Creative ways could be explored to present these materials within and alongside the chapters (e.g., in supplementary materials or with links). Some participants also noted that quantitative data can be important to consider and present, alongside qualitative descriptions and narratives, with a focus on highlighting and exploring connections and relevance of multiple knowledge systems in understanding complex biocultural processes.
- The assessment will require **a strategy for finding, gathering and assessing information**. This should ensure balanced representation and analysis across regions and sensitivity to the different terminologies and concepts used by different Indigenous Peoples and local communities, so that relevant materials can be found around key themes that may not be expressed in similar ways among different countries, communities and knowledge frameworks.
- **Case studies** will be a vital source of information, and a process is needed to ensure that these represent a diversity of communities, and that they are globally distributed. It will also be important to ensure that key lessons are being drawn from multiple studies, and that case studies are not giving the impression that ILK only has relevance in individual, local contexts (see point below).
- The assessment should adopt a clear **approach to managing, exploring and representing diversity**. The assessment may need to identify and highlight general themes and trends among Indigenous Peoples and local communities, but it will also be important to also highlight diversity and avoid generalizing.
- Applying a **regional lens** could help with analysis and representation of the distinct worldviews, policy settings and relationships between communities and their governments in different regions, as these can be very different in, for example, Canada, New Zealand, the

Philippines, Uganda and Brazil. Participants noted that sometimes IPBES findings are too general at the global level to be easily applied in regional or national contexts.

- The assessment presents an opportunity to demonstrate the **important contributions from Indigenous Peoples and local communities, including their customary governance systems, to biodiversity conservation and human wellbeing**, demonstrating that local level actions (which could be in part demonstrated through case studies) have global significance when considered cumulatively. Some participants highlighted that it will be important to leverage support and compensation for these contributions, as opposed to current situations where, in many cases, Indigenous contributions are ignored, or communities are actively endangered for protecting their lands. Participants also noted that in many countries achieving the KMGBF target of protecting 30% of lands and waters will require active engagement with Indigenous Peoples and their lands and territories.
- The assessment should explore and demonstrate ways in which **ILK systems can be addressed across scales**, noting that often there is uncertainty around how to move from diverse local examples and impacts to demonstrating significance at national, regional and global levels. This could include methods for scaling beyond individual case studies to show global significance, as well as exploring how ILK systems themselves can move across scales.
- A **review of the availability of information** and data on Indigenous Peoples and their contributions to biodiversity and wellbeing, in different locations and contexts, would also be an important contribution from the assessment. Participants pointed to the analysis of the usage of the headline, binary, component and complementary indicators and of national indicators in national reports being conducted by the Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD),² which is due in 2026, as a relevant initiative to follow. They also noted a significant amount of information and data exists at local levels, and is held in different ways by communities and researchers, and much of this may not be currently available to national reporting.
- It is crucial that **Indigenous Peoples and local communities validate their own knowledge within the assessment**, through workshops, reviews and consultation with the ILK task force, in accordance with IPBES rules and procedures. ILK should not be validated through “mainstream” or “western” science.
- **Strategies to work with diverse languages should be developed**, including the UN languages and Indigenous and local languages, recognizing that these are vital sources of knowledge as well as being mechanisms for communities to access and benefit from IPBES assessments.

² <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-16/cop-16-dec-31-en.pdf>

This could build on work and methods from previous assessments, such as nexus and transformative change.

- The assessment could explore **multiple pathways for ongoing engagement and communication with diverse knowledge holders** to maintain strong connections between communities, knowledge holders and the assessment process. Contributors should also be continuously informed of how their contributions are being used and they should have the opportunity to review drafts. Existing networks such as the Centres of Distinction on ILK and IIFBES can support these efforts, with due support from IPBES.
- A communication and outreach strategy should also be developed to include innovative, diverse formats for sharing and **communicating IPBES findings to communities, knowledge holders and decision-makers**, such as images, social media and other forms of publications, to ensure that results are useful and accessible.
- Clear guidance is needed on **how initiatives, examples, research and materials from Indigenous Peoples and local communities can be prioritised and appropriately acknowledged** in the assessment, including understanding and demonstrating data sovereignty principles and processes. The Saami Council's approach was highlighted as a useful example of these types of processes as well as work by Indigenous-led research consortia in the USA and Canada.
- The authors of the assessment may determine how **AI will be used in the assessment**, using as resource the upcoming guidelines on AI being developed by the Data Management Taskforce so there is clear guidance.

3.2 Overall key concepts and themes

Participants discussed key concepts that can form foundations to the work of the assessment, and which can be elaborated and explored by the assessment, particularly in chapter 2. Importantly, participants emphasized that these concepts should not only frame the work with ILK systems, but instead the entire assessment should seek to weave these concepts into its framing, structure and analysis, which could contribute to reimagining the purpose and core questions of the assessment. They include:

- **Biocultural diversity:** This concept recognizes that biodiversity and culture are inseparable, that humans are part of nature, that humans are dependent on other aspects of nature, and that nature is continuously shaped by human actions, spiritual connections and relationships. Conservation, restoration, wellbeing and other themes in the assessment can be guided by biocultural diversity as a central cross-cutting element. The creative work in the second global assessment will engage not only different disciplines but also different ways of life and diverse worldviews, a biocultural framework could offer a holistic perspective to

understand and bridge diverse knowledge systems. The cultural aspects of biocultural diversity may also extend beyond humans. Some animal species are recognized by science as having distinct “cultures”, for example orcas, and for many Indigenous Peoples and local communities this understanding is much broader, covering animals, plants, landscapes, spirits and other aspects of nature.

- **Nature:** Participants recommended an exploration of diverse conceptualizations of nature, and their impacts for policy and action on the ground. For example, a conceptual separation of nature and people, as is often seen in worldviews founded on science, can lead to Indigenous Peoples and local communities being removed from protected areas. Participants also noted that many Indigenous Peoples and local communities have different ways of expressing concepts that are similar to “nature”, which usually include biocultural connections or spirituality, as well as implications for the kinds of relationships that Indigenous Peoples and local communities value and the responsibilities that follow on from those relationships.

Examples

“Mother earth” or similar concepts are used by many Indigenous Peoples and local communities, but it is important to note that these are not global Indigenous concepts. Other communities may speak more of “country” (for example among **Aboriginal Australians**) or “land” (for example among many **First Nations communities in Canada and the USA**). There are also deeper nuances within this, for example, **Anishinaabeg in the USA and Canada** use the term *akiing* to refer to land and water as a place-relative, and the term *Ishkaakamikwe* to describe the female whole earth spirit/body relative, which is roughly synonymous with mother earth. As another example, **Mapuche people in Chile** describe the “*Wall Mapu*” or “all the land” where they identify the existence of a central earth and two other spiritual dimensions.

- **Spirituality:** A common theme among many Indigenous Peoples and local communities around the world is that of spiritual connections to nature, people, ancestors and future generations. Spirituality and ceremony are central to understanding Indigenous Peoples’ and local communities’ responsibilities and relationships with nature, the foundations of ILK systems and values and their transmission, as well as adaptive capacity and resilience to change.
- **Agency of non-humans and nature-centric approaches:** Many Indigenous ontologies and epistemologies recognize that non-human beings, such as animals and plants, landscapes and other natural entities, possess agency and intrinsic value independent of human interest. These perspectives emphasize reciprocal relationships between humans and other aspects of the natural world, in which humans are part of a broader web of life rather than its centre. From this view, other elements of nature can be conserved for their intrinsic value, not for what they give to humans.

- **Good quality of life:** This is a sub-section of chapter 3, and the concept of good quality of life may need to be introduced in chapter 2, reflecting biocultural relationships, responsibilities and spiritual connections (see discussion in section 3.5.2 below for chapter 3).
- **People's contribution to nature:** This concept encapsulates the diverse ways in which Indigenous Peoples and local communities, and others, can make positive contributions to nature, for example through land management and restoration. Participants in the workshop noted that this concept is not well demonstrated in the IPBES conceptual framework, as the graphical representation of the conceptual framework suggests unidirectional relations which can seem to only consider the ways that nature contributes to people. Thus, the diverse ways that Indigenous Peoples and local communities respect, manage, protect and create landscapes and seascapes, and maintain balance between humans and other aspects of nature, can be overlooked.³
- **Rights:**
 - **Indigenous rights**, as set out in the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) (also in line with the UN Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues (UNPFII), the Expert Mechanism on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (EMRIP), and the Special Rapporteur on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples) should be a foundation for all work with Indigenous Peoples, as well as human rights. Many Indigenous Peoples use their rights to assert and continue their protection of responsibilities and interrelationships that secure the sustainability of biocultural systems and non-human relatives within nature.
 - Meanwhile, human rights and other applicable rights should be a foundation for work with **local communities**, recognizing that local communities do not have a specific rights framework at global level.
 - **Rights of nature** are also important, but at times these can conflict with the rights of Indigenous Peoples, local communities and others living in these ecosystems or areas.
 - Rights-based approaches may also consider **biocultural rights**. While human rights and rights of nature can emphasize separation, biocultural rights affirm relationality and mutual connections between humans within nature.

³ Authors could review previous discussions on the conceptual framework as developed in the following papers:

- Díaz, Sandra, et al. "Assessing nature's contributions to people." *Science* 359.6373 (2018): 270-272. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap8826>
- Díaz, Sandra, and Unai Pascual. "Reciprocity towards nature in the biodiversity science–policy interface." *People and Nature* 7.5 (2025): 1129-1138. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.70033>

- **Land tenure**, including in marine and coastal areas, is one of the key rights that supports Indigenous Peoples and local communities to sustainably manage and use their landscapes and seascapes, and to maintain their responsibilities towards lands and waters, as well as to support community wellbeing, security and cultural continuity.
- Some participants also noted that while rights are important, they are not a final goal. They are instead a way of moving towards **justice**, and an evolving end goal of a **transformation of relationships** with each other and the natural world, enacted through responsibility.
- **Indigenous and traditional territories:** This concept recognizes that Indigenous Peoples and local communities are an inextricable part of their lands and waters, through biocultural connections including spirituality, practices on the land, knowledge systems, food systems, sustainable use and multiple other processes. Many Indigenous Peoples and local communities want to see these areas considered and recognized within efforts to meet targets for the KMGBF, including Target 3, in ways that enhance their stewardship and governance.
- **Governance, including customary governance:** Participants highlighted the importance of customary governance for managing biocultural diversity, avoiding conflicts and enhancing good quality of life. They noted that customary governance systems should therefore be a key theme explored throughout the assessment, including their mechanisms, benefits to biocultural diversity, threats and enabling conditions for continuation and revitalization. Overall, beyond customary governance, participants also noted that Indigenous Peoples and local communities must be part of governance across scales, that governance in all its forms across scales needs to be reimagined, and that customary governance and ILK systems can provide models and underlying values to support this reimagination.

Examples of customary governance

Among the Karamojong of **Uganda**, the *Akiriket* is a sacred assembly of senior elders, traditionally convened in natural spaces such as groves or rocky shrines. Elders in this forum deliberate on ecological changes and their implications for society. Decisions may include initiating land restoration, restricting the hunting of young or pregnant wildlife, regulating plant harvesting, initiating seasonal migration to allow pasture and water recovery, or promoting sustainable use of natural resources. Implementation is often entrusted to the *karachuna* (youth age group). These decisions are communicated to the wider community through dialogues, cultural ceremonies and campfire meetings. *Etamam* is also an important mechanism, as a council of elders who decide on land use and other issues. Elders may also send their youth as emissaries to discuss with other communities and explain their intention to bring their cattle to their areas. *Emurron*, or medicine men, are also important within customary governance. It could be important to explore how these customary governance systems function, their strengths and

benefits in terms of sustainable resource use and conflict avoidance and resolution, and how to support the continuation and resurgence of these governance mechanisms.

The customary governance of nature conservation under the Oromo Gada System in **Ethiopia**⁴ is rooted in Indigenous ecological knowledge that views land, forests and water as sacred foundations of community life. Among groups such as the Nole Maccaa Oromo of West Wallagga, natural resources are governed through customary laws (*Seera Gadaa*) that regulate access, use and protection of common resources. These laws are enacted and reviewed in assemblies such as the *Gumi Gayo* and implemented through decentralized institutions responsible for water wells, grazing lands, forests and wildlife. Practices like setting aside pasture reserves, protecting water sources, restricting tree cutting and ensuring equitable access demonstrate how environmental management is integrated into democratic decision-making and community participation. This system reflects an understanding that sustainable livelihoods depend on maintaining balance between people and nature, and that conservation must be enforced through culturally legitimate rules and institutions. Furthermore, Oromo Indigenous knowledge emphasizes a holistic worldview in which the physical, social and spiritual worlds are interconnected. Concepts such as *Safuu* (ethical respect and harmony) and *Ayyaana* (spiritual life force) guide behavior toward nature, teaching that humans are custodians responsible for maintaining ecological balance and respecting all forms of life. This worldview shapes conservation practices such as protecting sacred trees and ritual sites, regulating hunting and imposing sanctions on environmental violations, including declaring wildlife species protected under Gada law. Such customary governance ensures that natural resource management is not only practical but also moral and spiritual, promoting coexistence, biodiversity protection and long-term environmental sustainability within Oromo society. Recognizing its unique role in preserving cultural identity, social organization and environmental stewardship, UNESCO inscribed the Gada system on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2016.

⁴ For more information, see:

- [Oromo Indigenous Knowledge and Practices in Natural Resources Management Land Forest and Water in Focus](#)
- [Beyond the commonality and expression of Oromo civilization: the mediating role of gada system for commons management of natural resources](#)
- [Oromo Oral Literature for Environmental Conservation: A Study of Selected Folksongs in East and West Hararghe Zones](#)
- [Indigenous institutions and wildlife conservation: The case of the Oromo Gada System protecting Swayne's hartebeest in Ethiopia](#)

- **Self-determination:** The UNDRIP affirms the inherent right of Indigenous Peoples to self-determination, a principle that remains a central aspiration for many Indigenous communities worldwide. It is essential that Chapter 2 and the broader assessment reflect this principle as a foundational consideration. For example, many Indigenous Peoples seek to restore or reclaim full jurisdiction of their lands and waters, rather than being part of co-management arrangements, which often in reality do not function well for Indigenous Peoples. Building an evidence base to show Indigenous and local community successes around conservation management and customary governance could support governments in recognizing that restoring Indigenous control of lands and waters can be an effective way of ensuring biodiversity conservation, health and human wellbeing.
- **Language:** As discussed above for the approach to the assessment, it will be important to recognize the crucial importance of language for expressing concepts, philosophies and values. Languages and practices embed knowledge of socio-ecological systems and also enable the transfer of that knowledge. They also provide a record of observations and remind Indigenous Peoples and local communities of their responsibilities and relationships. Many terms and concepts in Indigenous and local languages, and the knowledge that they convey, are not easily translated into other languages, and much can be lost. Conversely, it will be important to recognize the ways that the predominance of “mainstream” scientific terminology and concepts can enforce and privilege one set of values and worldviews within an assessment.
- **Diversity and plurality:** Recognizing and exploring the global diversity of Indigenous Peoples and of local communities will be essential. Diversity also exists within single communities, for example, between elders and youth, women and men, hunters and business owners. A balance between recognizing diversity and recognizing and highlighting commonalities and overarching concepts and principles between Indigenous Peoples and local communities will be required for the assessment, whilst not implying that all communities think and act the same way. The possibility of developing a framework to represent ILK systems and worldviews was discussed, recognizing that this would be challenging if the full diversity of ILK systems, communities, values and worldviews is to be reflected.

3.3 Terminology

Participants discussed key terminology used by IPBES. This included “**Indigenous Peoples and local communities**”. This is the terminology currently used by IPBES to describe these groups. However, there are ongoing tensions regarding its use. Many Indigenous Peoples have called for the two terms, “Indigenous Peoples” and “local communities”, to be separated, while others want to keep them connected, as this facilitates the inclusion and participation of Indigenous groups and others who are not recognized as Indigenous by their governments. It was noted that

working at the global level, broad terms need to be found that may not be suitable in every national or local context. There are however important distinctions between Indigenous Peoples and local communities at the global level in terms of rights frameworks (see above). All authors are asked to read the conceptualization of local communities in section 2 of the IPBES ILK Methodological Guidance,⁵ which aims to set out an understanding of what this term means and which communities it would include.

Participants also noted that the **definitions of ILK systems shown in the existing glossary** can be revisited and analysed to see if they need developing further for this assessment. Other aspects of ILK systems, for example how ILK systems conceptualize “methods” may also need to be considered. Diverse terminologies, including “Indigenous science”, may also need to be explored, noting that some Indigenous Peoples wish to use this term while others do not. Overall, a coherent definition of ILK systems may need to be developed for the assessment.

3.4 Chapter 2: Different knowledge systems and the role of Indigenous Peoples and local communities

Participants discussed the scope of chapter 2 and its connections with other chapters. In particular, they highlighted that:

- Chapter 2 is a **significant opportunity** for Indigenous Peoples and local communities to deepen and broaden the representation and analysis of ILK in the assessment, and to expand participation. They also noted a **challenge or risk** that the chapter is disconnected from the rest of the assessment, and highlighted that specific approaches may be applied to ensure that this is not the case, as described above.
- The scoping document calls for an **exploration of the diverse and plural values and world views of Indigenous Peoples and local communities all over the world, drawing out common themes**. Participants noted that this represents a significant challenge, due to the vast diversity of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (as discussed above). Participants also discussed the appropriateness of developing a common framework for the worldviews of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, noting that such a framework does not currently exist, and that it may not be appropriate to attempt one, given the difficulty for such a framework to account for the global diversity of Indigenous and local worldviews and the risk that some worldviews are prioritised over others. They noted that a better approach may be to bring together diverse frameworks that have already been produced by

⁵ See: [IPBES ILK MethodGuide 12MAR2024.pdf](#)

communities or Indigenous organizations around the world, or that could be produced on request, to then draw out common themes and key differences between them. Applying a regional view and ensuring regional balance could support drawing out common themes. There may also be other ways of grouping worldviews, for example by livelihoods, which could include pastoralists, fishers, hunters, farmers and others.

- Participants expressed the view that the [IPBES conceptual framework](#) does not sufficiently reflect the worldviews of Indigenous Peoples and local communities as it is largely built on scientific framings and terminology, with only partial acknowledgement of comparable Indigenous concepts. They observed that the framework also reinforces a separation between people and nature, and it does not specifically acknowledge “people’s contributions to nature”, as discussed above. While Chapter 2 is required to engage with the IPBES conceptual framework, as requested by the Plenary in the scoping document, some participants suggested that the chapter could also explain, based on the assessed evidence, why the framework may not be fully appropriate, and to illustrate options to improve it, informed by the findings of the assessment.
- Chapter 2 can play a significant role in **exploring and assessing knowledge co-production methods and mechanisms and developing a knowledge co-production pathway**, to inform both the rest of the assessment and broader audiences who will read the assessment. This could in part be done by exploring and critically assessing key concepts, such as the multiple evidence-base approach, “bridging”, “braiding” and “weaving”, two-eyed and three-eyed seeing (Canada) and double-hulled canoes (New Zealand). These different concepts explore how diverse knowledge systems can co-exist, converge and work together, and also the different methods for supporting this work. Importantly, these knowledge systems can also stand alone with their own internal validity and authority.

3.5 Chapter 3: Status and trends

3.5.1 Overall structure

Participants noted that the **four subsections of the chapter, on good quality of life, direct and indirect drivers, nature and nature’s contributions to people, enforce a separation in concepts** that for Indigenous Peoples and local communities would be inextricably linked, for example between people and nature. They emphasized that an approach will be needed to explore these concepts from a holistic standpoint that reflects Indigenous and local biocultural worldviews.

3.5.2 Good quality of life

Participants welcomed the inclusion of good quality of life as a topic for analysis, and emphasised that for many Indigenous Peoples and local communities, good quality of life includes their

relationships with territories, lands, waters and community, including ancestors and future generations, in a cycle of wellbeing that includes the responsibilities that members of Indigenous Peoples and local communities hold towards their communities, territories, lands and waters, within reciprocal relationships. These relationships are maintained in part through practices on the land, as well as spirituality, stories and languages.

Participants also observed that many Indigenous worldviews include notions of “life” that go **beyond human, or even biological, dimensions**, to include, for example, the life infused in landscapes, mountains and rocks. This could be accounted for when discussing good quality of life in the subchapter.

Participants highlighted that Indigenous and local perceptions of wellbeing offer **global lessons**, shifting focus from individuality and material wealth to collective and biocultural wellbeing.

Examples

Participants from **New Zealand** highlighted work with Māori communities that explores Indigenous conceptions of health and well-being, including spirituality and connection to land, and indicators based on these. These have been embedded in policy. This work and these processes could provide useful examples for the sub-chapter.

The Northern Territories of **Australia** also has a wellbeing framework that considers multiple values around wellbeing.⁶

A participant from **Peru** noted that in Quechua communities, the concept of *Allin Kawsay* offers insights into living well in harmony with nature and serves as a framework for studying sustainable food systems grounded in reciprocity, relationality, and environmental care.

Participants also noted that **traditional medicine**, which also includes traditional diets, rituals and ceremonies, constitutes an important dimension of discussions of good quality of life. Declines in traditional medicines and foods, which are often replaced by “western” medicines and diets, were identified as key drivers of changing perceptions and experiences of wellbeing and good quality of life among many Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The sub-chapter could explore trends and impacts around these issues.

Participants noted that these conceptualizations of good quality of life discussed above then lead to recognition of the importance of **rights to a healthy environment, rights to land, rights to water and other aspects of biocultural systems**.

Participants recommended the analysis of good quality of life could include **human rights** dimensions and an assessment of trends in rights violations, including harassment and killings of

⁶ For more information on the examples from New Zealand and Australia, see: [Remaking the Sustainable Development Goals: relational Indigenous epistemologies](#)

environmental and Indigenous defenders, forced displacements and developments proceeding without FPIC, which all significantly impact good quality of life and also biodiversity management and conservation by Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

Participants also noted that many Indigenous Peoples and local communities are particularly impacted by **health challenges**. For example, in Africa, air pollution may have significant impacts.⁷ This could also be explored in the sub-chapter.

Participants also noted that reconsideration of good quality of life from Indigenous worldviews could have **cascading effects on other components of the chapter**, such as drivers (direct and indirect), nature and nature's contributions to people.

3.5.3 Indicators

Participants discussed the need to develop indicators for ILK that would support tracking trends in nature, drivers and the wellbeing of Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

3.5.3.1 Measuring wellbeing

Participants noted that the assessment could support the development of **appropriate indicators** to measure Indigenous and local community conceptualizations of quality of life, to support global and national calls to move **beyond Gross Domestic Product** as a measure, by exploring alternative ways of understanding and measuring wellbeing in diverse contexts, including specific indicators. For many Indigenous Peoples and local communities, the strength of relationships (within the community and with other aspects of nature), knowledge systems and spirituality better reflect wellbeing and quality of life than financial metrics. Participants also noted that the drive to enhance GDP may cause further degradation of nature and violations of community rights, so GDP may in some cases be a cause of declines in community wellbeing, rather than an indicator of positive trends. However, participants also cautioned that many Indigenous Peoples and local communities are now tied to market systems and economies, so it should not be stated that they exist outside of these processes and do not need to be considered within them.

Participants also noted that other indices used to measure wellbeing are often not able to include Indigenous Peoples and local communities fully or on their own terms. Many indexes are not intended to measure broadly, for example the Human Development Index, or they are set up to rely on national indicators that do not include community-level data. However, these indexes, and GDP, continue to play a significant role in discussions of wellbeing and development globally and locally.

⁷ See for example the World Bank report [here](#).

A participant noted that many of these discussions link to the **Capability Approach** to measuring wellbeing, which aim to measure what communities are able to do and be, and their freedoms to choose and decide on their futures, rather than only measuring their functioning at some particular time. This approach can provide a richer account of community wellbeing.

As a result, many communities around the world are **developing their own wellbeing indexes**.

Example

Some Indigenous communities in the **Arctic** have added indicators such as “how much food the community gets from nature”, “fate control” (the extent that they are able to make decisions) and “cultural vitality” to indicators of the Community Wellbeing Index, to enhance the ways they can reflect community wellbeing.⁸

During a previous IPBES ILK dialogue workshop in **the Philippines**, an Indigenous Aeta community was asked for an indicator of wellbeing for their community in the future. They explained that if a sacred *dance of the fish* is still performed by future generations, this will be a sign that the community and nature are still in a good relationship.

Also, participants warned against considering some indicators such as “**access to education**” as an indicator of good quality of life, as in many cases inappropriate education systems are a cause of declines in culture and ILK. Such indicators need to be approached with nuance to capture the full range of impacts of education systems, as well as the breadth of educational systems, which would include traditional customary education in Indigenous communities including Indigenous languages, practices and technologies.

Participants recommended the following resources:

- The **Human Development Reports**, which in 2026 are expected to include the Nature Relationship Index.⁹
- The **Ārramāt Project**,¹⁰ which focuses on research around the importance of the whole environment, including biodiversity, to the health and wellbeing of communities.

3.5.3.2 Local indicators

Participants discussed the importance of **local indicators**, including those tied to ecological calendars that support forecasting and decision-making on seasonal cycles, for example among pastoralists in Uganda.

⁸ See also the summary of the project description for the Arctic Social Indicators Project [here](#).

⁹ See: <https://hdr.undp.org/nature-relationship-index> and also <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-025-09080-1>

¹⁰ See: <https://arramatproject.org/>

Indigenous and local indicators are often embedded in **Indigenous and local languages**, for example, languages may encode nuanced ways of understanding seasonal cycles or connections between species.

Participants noted that increasingly, such indicators may be challenged by **climate change**, which is causing disruptions in ecological patterns and seasons. This highlights the importance of restoring and protecting Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' ability to maintain cultural ways of life, languages and foodways for understanding, sharing, transmitting and adapting indicators.

A participant noted that in terms of monitoring impacts on and trends in biocultural systems, a good indicator could be whether communities are still carrying out their **traditional activities and practices**, and how these have adapted or changed with time, as this demonstrates the link between people and their lands and waters.

A participant recommended **Indigenous monitoring networks** as potential sources of indicators and information. However, she noted that often this information is confidential, or is only available at the community level, so communication and engagement may be required so that communities can decide if they wish to share. An example is the First Nations National Guardians Network (NGN)¹¹ in Canada, which is a national non-profit that aims to support First Nations-led stewardship and sovereignty through First Nations Guardians initiatives, by providing consistent funding, networking, training, and education opportunities that support the profession of Guardians.

Participants also highlighted that there are challenges in **moving from local, holistic, community and context specific indicators to national or global levels**. They noted that if chapter 3 could explore mechanisms, methods or examples by which these local indicators could inform national and global level processes, for example through NBSAPs, this would be an important contribution.

3.5.3.3 *National-level indicators and processes*

Participants also noted that other relevant indicators may already exist at **national levels**, and exploring these and bringing them together would be an important contribution from chapter 3.

Example

With the adoption of the KMGBF, **the Philippines** underwent a process of aligning the Philippine Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (PBSAP) with the new global framework. Indigenous Peoples and support groups, who were not visible in the formulation of the previous PBSAP, saw this as an opportunity to collectively contribute to effective and inclusive biodiversity policies and

¹¹ See: <https://www.rng-ngn.ca/about/>

actions, to ensure the recognition of the rights, commitments and contributions of Indigenous Peoples to biodiversity conservation, sustainable use and benefit sharing.

Indigenous groups and communities convened and facilitated their own independent process in formulating an **Indigenous Peoples' Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (IPBSAP)**.

This was done during a series of national and inter-regional roundtable discussions, focusing on capacity-building and consensus-building process towards articulating and formulating Indigenous Peoples' perspectives, concerns, issues, targets, contributions and commitments to biodiversity conservation, sustainable use and benefit sharing. Overall, thirty Indigenous Peoples Organizations representing Indigenous communities all over the Philippines were involved, along with NGOs and some government representatives.

The IPBSAP is a document that serves as a collective commitment by Indigenous Peoples about their roles and responsibilities, traditional knowledge, values, rights and interrelationships with their territories and biodiversity. It is the first of its kind in the world.

It provides an overview of the status and context of biodiversity in Indigenous Peoples' lands and territories in the Philippines. It also communicates the key contributions and commitments by Indigenous Peoples to biodiversity conservation and sustainable use in the Philippines. It puts forward key issues and recommendations on biodiversity from the perspectives of Indigenous Peoples and serves as a guiding document for Indigenous Peoples in carrying out biodiversity actions.

The IPBSAP process also **developed indicators for all 23 KMGBF targets**, with different communities showing more interest in some targets than others, depending what was most relevant to their circumstances and contexts. They did not diverge too much from what the government had started, and instead reinterpreted this from the Indigenous perspective, for example by bringing knowledge and aspirations for Indigenous ancestral domains to targets for protected areas.

As a recognition of this work, the head of the Philippine Delegation to CBD COP16, welcomed the IPBSAP.

Next steps include localization and target setting for the actions in the IPBSAP. Indigenous Peoples were very enthusiastic to contribute to the targets and iron out commitments.

3.5.3.4 *Global-level indicators*

Participants also explained that Indigenous Peoples have been working at **global levels** to develop indicators and processes to support monitoring in ways that are culturally relevant and appropriate.

Example and discussion: Global scale indicators

Global indicators on traditional knowledge have been developed for the CBD and KMGBF, in a process that started in 2004 through a series of workshops and other processes. These were then further adapted for the KMGBF through a series of workshops and expert groups.¹² The indicators are:

- Linguistic diversity and number of speakers of Indigenous languages
- Land use change and land tenure in the traditional territories of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities
- Practice of traditional occupations
- Degree to which traditional knowledge and practices are respected through the appropriate and respectful integration, participation and safeguards in the national implementation of the strategic plan.

The KMGBF includes a framework that aims to oversee monitoring of its goals and targets. The traditional knowledge indicators are seen as crosscutting across the framework, and the new Subsidiary Body on 8(j) is responsible for overseeing this.

The CBD will also produce a global report on collective progress in the implementation of the KMGBF, to be released at COP17 in 2026. This is created mostly by compiling information from national reports. Governments have started their national reports, and will need to submit them early in 2026. Indigenous Peoples and local communities have two ways of contributing, either by being included in their governments' reports, or through a call the CBD is releasing for case studies, and some groups of Indigenous Peoples and local communities are aiming to contribute.

In practice, content relating to Indigenous Peoples and local communities may be limited in the global report on collective progress in the implementation of the KMGBF, and so a coalition of Indigenous Peoples and local communities are also producing the third Local Biodiversity Outlook (LBO)¹³ as a parallel process. As with the previous two LBOs, this will include analysis and synthesis of progress and next steps based on extensive collation of case studies and examples from Indigenous Peoples and local communities around the world. It may be important for the second global assessment to follow and analyse these processes, as well as to use the LBOs and their materials as resources.

¹² See for example:

- <https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/283e/eb7c/6a953a1e098b6c46e0f3be8d/sbstta-26-inf-11-en.pdf>
- <https://transformativepathways.net/experts-work-on-assessing-status-of-traditional-knowledge-indicators-for-the-global-biodiversity-framework/>

¹³ See: <https://localbiodiversityoutlooks.net/>

Also at the global level, the *Indigenous Navigator*¹⁴ is another important resource, which provides a framework and a set of tools developed by and for Indigenous Peoples to systematically monitor implementation of their rights, following the framework set out by the UNDRIP. It has become a way for Indigenous Peoples to provide their own data at the global level, which sometimes does not align with national reporting by governments. A participant recommended that authors of the second global assessment familiarize themselves with the indicators in the Indigenous Navigator.

Participants also noted that the *IPBES assessment of monitoring biodiversity* is also working on some of these themes connected to indicators, monitoring and ILK at different scales, and this could be an important resource.

3.5.4 Drivers

3.5.4.1 Negative drivers

Participants highlighted **colonialism and capitalism** as key underlying causes of many of the negative impacts to biocultural systems seen today, and emphasized that these should be highlighted and explored throughout the assessment and particularly in discussions around drivers.

Participants also emphasized the negative impacts of **harassment and violence towards environmental defenders and Indigenous Peoples and local communities, as well as forced displacement**. These not only greatly impact wellbeing, but also the ability of communities and individuals to protect and manage their lands, which can lead to significant reductions in biodiversity. Conflicts, including conflicts around natural resources, can also be significant negative drivers on biodiversity and the wellbeing of Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

Extractive industries, monoculture, forestry, deforestation, agricultural expansion and land degradation were also highlighted as key negative drivers on biocultural systems, including some developments that are intended to be “green”, for example on Saami lands in Norway, where reindeer herding lands are becoming sites for green energy. **Climate change and invasive species** were also noted as having negative impacts on Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

Participants noted that **loss of lands and waters or loss of access to lands and waters** is a significant negative driver for biocultural wellbeing. Participants highlighted that for many Indigenous communities this occurred due to colonial processes, and in many cases those lands have not been returned, leading to ongoing exclusion and inability to access for harvesting or stewardship. This represents an ongoing negative impact on biocultural wellbeing. Processes of displacement and loss of access to lands are also continuing in many countries, due to industrial

¹⁴ See: <https://indigenoustravel.org/>

development or as new actors move into an area and buy land. Often the communities nearby do not know who owns the land or how to participate in or prevent this process, as is seen for example among Mapuche communities in Chile.

Participants also highlighted that **biodiversity conservation and protected areas** can be negative drivers on biocultural systems, as in some cases Indigenous Peoples and local communities are removed from their lands as part of efforts to conserve nature. Programmes like REDD+,¹⁵ nature-based solutions and new biodiversity credit schemes, all risk exacerbating evictions and conflicts if they are not managed well, and if biocultural systems and human and Indigenous rights are not set as core foundations. Participants therefore noted that “western” conceptualizations of nature as separate from humans, and nature as inherently at risk from all human activities, can be seen as an underlying cause and driver of biocultural loss.

Participants noted that loss of knowledge, language and value systems of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, and alienation from their lands and waters, are negative drivers that cause declines in both biodiversity and human wellbeing. For example, a participant noted that loss of language among some Indigenous groups in Canada could impact their ability to monitor and manage their lands and waters, as indicators of change are tied to language. This loss of knowledge therefore impacts biodiversity.

Participants also highlighted that **extractive research processes** are a negative driver on knowledge systems. These research processes often take knowledge from communities but do not provide benefits to communities, or support knowledge transmission within communities. These experiences have led to a widespread reluctance by many communities to share ILK, which means a loss of opportunities for wider restoration of biocultural systems and wellbeing, as important knowledge is not shared.

Participants stressed that it is important to analyse all of these intertwining drivers through a **biocultural approach** that recognizes that impacts on nature also impact people, and vice versa, as one intertwined system. They also noted that the drivers of the current crisis in biodiversity are closely tied to processes of oppressing Indigenous Peoples and local communities and their knowledge and practices.

Example – multiple drivers on bicultural wellbeing

In south-east **Ethiopia**, particularly in areas such as the Borana zone and the Liben and Afder zones of Somali Region, recurrent droughts linked to climate change have forced the government to promote the traditional pastoral Oromo and Somali communities to shift toward agro-pastoral

¹⁵ “REDD” stands for Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation in Developing Countries, and the ‘+’ stands for additional forest-related activities that protect the climate, namely sustainable management of forests and the conservation and enhancement of forest carbon stocks.

farming as a coping mechanism. While crop cultivation (such as maize and sorghum) provides short-term food security, it often reduces herd mobility, which is a cornerstone of pastoral ILK. For example, among the Borana Oromo, traditional rotational grazing systems, dry-season pasture reserves (*kallo*), and customary water governance around deep wells (*tulaa*) are based on herd mobility and seasonal movement. When households settle permanently to farm, these mobility-based institutions weaken, communal rangelands fragment and customary authorities lose influence over land-use regulation. This transformation can erode ILK in several ways. First, knowledge of pasture ecology, livestock breeding adapted to drought and customary drought forecasting becomes less central to livelihoods. Second, sacred natural sites and grazing reserves may be converted into farmland, undermining conservation norms embedded in the Gada system and related customary laws. In parts of Borana, enclosure of communal rangeland for private cultivation has disrupted collective grazing management and reduced biodiversity. Similarly, in agro-pastoral pockets in Liben in the Guji-Borana borderlands, increasing cultivation along seasonal rivers has altered traditional floodplain management practices. Although agro-pastoralism helps communities cope with rainfall variability, the reduced reliance on pastoral mobility and communal governance structures risks gradual erosion of ILK systems that historically sustained both ecological balance and social cohesion in south-east Ethiopia.

3.5.4.2 Positive drivers

As discussed above in section 3.2, participants also emphasized the importance of considering “**people’s contributions to nature**”, noting that ILK systems and land and water management and governance by Indigenous Peoples and local communities can be important positive drivers for good quality of life and nature. Coupled revitalization of ILK and restoration of landscapes and seascapes can also be important positive drivers.

Example

Caldwell First Nation in **Canada** hosted a day of field and community visits during the workshop. As a once-displaced, off-reserve First Nation community, they are slowly reclaiming lands across their traditional territory. They have purchased a farm that has since been restored to a wetland, plant medicine and food garden near Windsor, Ontario. During the workshop they held a first Anishnaabe water ceremony for the site, led by women, with diverse community members participating, including elders and youth. This helped to demonstrate how Indigenous ownership and management can be a positive driver of ecological restoration, and support community members to restore their relationships with land and water. It also demonstrated the important role of women in many Indigenous cultures, and how restoration of lands and waters can also support ILK systems and culture, as these are inseparable within biocultural systems.

In Michigan, in the **United States**, Anishinaabe communities are leading projects that aim to restore traditional burning practices, in collaborations with federal government. This follows a

growing realisation that traditional *ishkode* (fire) management practices were of benefit to the ecosystems around the Great Lakes.

3.5.5 Nature

Participants noted that elders and harvesters in Indigenous communities often have **detailed knowledge of changes in trends** in lands, waters, animals, plants and community activities, and that these can be documented to gain a better understanding of changes in nature.

Participants noted that analysis of Indigenous lands, looking at **positive impacts of Indigenous management**, but also impacts of negative drivers, could provide important evidence to support Indigenous land management and also to highlight the need to mitigate negative drivers.

Participants also noted that **declines in agrobiodiversity** are of significant concern to many Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

Participants highlighted that attention to **mapping of coastal and marine areas** would also be important, to extend the understanding of areas under Indigenous management. This could include consideration of differing degrees of management, such as ownership, co-management, reserved rights or other means of access, noting that arrangements or practices may be officially recognized or, in some cases, taking place informally.

A participant emphasized that it would also be important to recognize that that **monocrop plantations** are not “forests”, as seems to be claimed by some proponents and mechanisms for monitoring forest cover.

3.6 Chapter 4: Future pathways

3.6.1 Concepts, philosophies and values

Participants emphasized the need to centre **Indigenous and local worldviews and values as foundations** for scenarios. They noted that it is important to consider who is visioning futures, who those futures are being visioned for, and the tools that are used. For example, many Indigenous Peoples and local communities engage in visioning as part of their lives and as part of their relationships and responsibilities, rather than as part of academic scenarios exercises.

Participants highlighted that it is also important to explore and highlight the **assumptions on which “scientific” scenarios are based**, for example that time is linear and that the future can be predicted through a linear connection extrapolated from the past and present. Meanwhile, many Indigenous Peoples and local communities view **time as cyclical**, with the present and future intertwined.

A participant also shared that scenarios work with Indigenous Peoples and local communities often reveals **multiple branching, converging and intersecting futures**, that are broader and more complex than the standard lines and targets that seem to be desired by many “mainstream” scientific approaches.

Participants noted that **Indigenous concepts and philosophies** can set different timelines and foundations for scenarios. Intergenerationality is key for many Indigenous Peoples and local communities when they think about the future, and many Indigenous communities teach that it is important to think seven, thirteen or more generations into the future and past, to ensure that activities today are supporting and not jeopardising future wellbeing, and also that they are honouring and carrying out the vision and work of the ancestors. Indigenous prophecies can also provide explorations of the future, for example the Seven Fires Prophecy among the Anishinaabe, who see themselves as living within a sacred story that weaves past, present and future. Also, in New Zealand and the Pacific, it is often said that “we walk forwards into the past and backwards into the future” as a recognition that the past is known, but the future cannot be seen.¹⁶ Other Indigenous concepts and philosophies about the future may not be clearly visible or expressed, but may instead be embedded in governance systems, and management and protection of lands, waters and livelihoods, education systems, or in sustainable economies and cooperatives established by some communities. Participants also highlighted the importance of centring nature within scenarios, and not only focusing on human-centric values.

Some participants also noted that many Indigenous Peoples focus on desired futures, and how to move towards them, even if they cannot be reached at present, rather than only focusing on a more limited range of possible futures. They are therefore often **aligned with visions for transformation and transformative change**, which some governments do not seem to align with, as it implies fundamental changes to economic and governance systems.

Participants highlighted the **Transformative Change Assessment** as a key resource, featuring visions from Indigenous Peoples (in Chapter 2) and clear roles and responsibilities for creating transformative change. In particular, the assessment emphasized that many Indigenous Peoples and local communities are already living sustainable lifestyles so may not need to change. Meanwhile, “mainstream” societies and economic, value and governance systems may need to transform. Participants also highlighted that transformative change entails shifting from an emphasis on instrumental and intrinsic values to relational values.

However, other participants also noted that some Indigenous Peoples and local communities have become **colonized by outside values and worldviews**, often due to deliberate strategies

¹⁶ See page 5 of: [Reimagining the Human Environment Relationship: Indigenous Philosophy and Intergenerational Justice](#)

imposed on them during colonialism that continue today. They may therefore also need to work on cultural revitalization and returning to values and priorities that are more connected to nature and holistic wellbeing. There are however many obstacles to this, as “mainstream” economies, education and society all work to further reinforce imposed values and worldviews.

Participants further emphasized the importance of engaging on positive scenarios and **positive visions for inspiring hope and action**, rather than only engaging around negative futures which can limit vision and hope and create feelings of hopelessness or frustration. This perspective on the need for positive visions is often closer to the traditional teachings from the elders, which are often closely aligned to building community strength and adaptability to carry them forward into the future. Nurturing positive energy, rather than dwelling on the negatives and problems, is an essential part of this.

Example

Some Inuit communities in **Canada** have found that the constant negative predictions from science, for example around climate change, denigrate the land and their home, and they risk creating negativity in their communities. They therefore also want to focus on the strength and adaptability of their communities, for example on ways in which they can relate to and harvest new animals that are arriving due to the warming climate.

For Anishinaabe communities in **Canada and the United States**, all beings in Creation received instructions to help one another (plants and animals included), and building positive futures is therefore an important responsibility for all beings.

3.6.2 Positive scenarios

Participants outlined key **foundations for positive future visions and pathways**, which included biocultural restoration, revitalization and resurgence, Indigenous sustainable self-determination, collective continuance and intergenerationality, and respect for rights and ILK systems. This could include, for example, scenarios based on Indigenous self-governance, or on full Indigenous jurisdiction of protected areas, and the impacts of this on biocultural systems. Food systems and food sovereignty also offer important pathways to positive futures, for example in the Philippines where communities are revitalizing home gardens (see example below). Participants noted that it will be important for positive future visions discussed in chapter 4 to connect with the conceptualizations and discussions of good quality of life in earlier chapters.

Indigenous responsibility and duties towards people, lands and waters, were also highlighted as important aspects of Indigenous sustainable self-determination, recognizing that reclaiming and revitalizing responsibilities and duties of care are part of reclaiming rights and ensuring good futures.

Participants also highlighted another important resource, the ***Transitions Toward Living in Harmony with Nature*** in the second edition of the Local Biodiversity Outlooks.¹⁷ These were developed through an analysis of multiple case studies and visions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities from across the world to draw out key synergies and themes. They can potentially form a framework for exploring pathways and visions from Indigenous Peoples and local communities. Some participants observed that transformative changes, rather than smooth transitions, could be required in some biocultural contexts.

Examples

In **the Philippines**, when some communities were threatened by industrial development around geothermal projects, they revitalized the use of traditional gongs and ceremonies, which revitalized community unity and cohesion. Revitalizing the building of canoes also enhanced community and culture in other areas. Moreover, many groups are revitalizing home gardens and heirloom seeds and promoting traditional foods as a way of enhancing food security and sovereignty, and revitalizing and strengthening cultural connections between the communities and their lands.¹⁸ This shows the ways that different pathways can lead to good futures for communities.

In **Canada and the United States of America**, First Nations communities are working together as part of the “Buffalo Treaty”, which aims to bring buffalo back to the prairies, recognizing the important role that this animal plays in relationships, identity, food systems and other aspects of biocultural systems, with a view to connecting with the past to create a better future for people and the animals.

In **Canada** efforts to reinstate practices around traditional burning are founded on a recognition that these practices are beneficial to forests, including by reducing large-scale wildfires. This also shows how the past is being brought into the future.

Participants shared examples of how Indigenous Peoples and local communities are discussing and working for their futures. Often this work is focused on **younger generations**, recognizing that they are future stewards of biocultural systems. Programmes and projects that prioritize Indigenous education, and reconnecting youth to culture, values, language, lands and waters, are often deemed essential for continuity. Participants also noted however that there are growing challenges, as many youth are increasingly disconnected from their cultures and values, as technology and other modern influences compete for their attention.

¹⁷ See: <https://lbo2.localbiodiversityoutlooks.net/transitions-towards-living-in-harmony-with-nature/>

¹⁸ A book will soon be published by the Network of the Centres of Distinction on ILK, on revitalizing Indigenous food systems, and this could be an important resource for the assessment. See: <https://www.codilk.org/>

Example

In **the Philippines**, Indigenous education programmes and activities to revitalize knowledge transmission have included immersion programmes (where youth from urban areas can go to live with a rural community), documentation of Indigenous knowledge and Indigenous learning festivals.

3.6.3 Negative scenarios

Participants also discussed **negative scenarios**, as a recognition that in many cases current trends are not positive. Negative scenarios could include continuation or worsening of ongoing challenges seen today, including conflict between Indigenous Peoples and local communities and conservation agencies, governments, and business and industry, displacement, cultural loss and disregard for Indigenous, human and biocultural rights, as well as climate change and other degradations of the environment. Shocks such as conflicts and pandemics, and their impacts on Indigenous Peoples and local communities, could also be considered.

A participant also noted that many governmental discussions around climate change focus on loss and damage in economic terms, whereas the important context of **biocultural loss and damage**, and its related impacts, needs to be given similar attention.

3.6.4 Methods and approaches

Participants emphasized that engaging with **qualitative information** and storytelling can be important methods for working with visions of the future and scenarios from Indigenous Peoples and local communities. It is also important to move away from scenarios based only on mathematical models, which are often seen as poor reflections of reality, as they lose important information when they try to simplify complex biocultural systems.

Participants noted that the **Natures Futures Framework** may not be the most appropriate framing for values systems from an Indigenous perspective, as many Indigenous Peoples and local communities would not separate their values into relational, intrinsic or instrumental categories. Participants also noted that the Natures Futures Framework should be viewed as a simple tool, rather than something that can engage deeply with the diversity of values, and as such it might help to navigate difference and support convergence. Overall, participants recommended that different ways of framing and organizing scenarios and visions could be explored.

Some participants noted that **modelling of Indigenous lands** can also be important, but these more quantitative methods should be combined with qualitative methods that give space for narratives of futures and pathways and also for data sovereignty.

Examples

Some communities have engaged in mapping of their lands, for example in **the Philippines** where they have mapped past and present land use, and important areas, such as sacred sites and

hunting areas. This effort has included and supported planning for the future, as it helps to prioritise places that need to be protected for community and cultural continuity. These types of projects could contribute to NBSAPs and also chapter 4 of the second global assessment.

The national ecosystem assessment of **Thailand** is aiming to include scenarios based on the knowledge of Indigenous communities living along the coast. This could be a useful resource for chapter 4 of the second global assessment.

A participant also shared that in Saami lands in **Norway**, communities have engaged in mapping projects to show past and present pastures for reindeer, to demonstrate how the available space has diminished as roads and wind turbines and other developments have taken up space on the land. They have also mapped hunting areas, fishing spots, berry picking areas and others. These types of projects can help to show trends in biocultural systems.

Participants noted that **other important resources** could include Indigenous declarations made in different fora at different scales (e.g., global, national), education plans, life plans, community plans and other processes and documents where Indigenous Peoples and local communities have expressed their visions for the future and potential pathways to reach them. While these may not be clearly labelled or conveyed as “scenarios”, they could also be used to explore scenarios and good futures from the perspectives of Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

Example

In Oaxaca, **Mexico**, Indigenous communities may not always actively talk about the future, but they are always planning for the future, for example through forest protection activities. In communities like Capulálpam de Méndez, youth also have to spend time on the land and participate in collective activities to create relationships with the land. Moreover, some communities have developed *Ordenamientos Comunitarios* (Community Based Land Used Plans) that include a vision for their community in 30 or 50 years. These plans serve as a tool for planning how to manage territories and resources and their bio-economies. These plans could be a resource for chapter 4.

3.7 Chapter 5: Options for action

Participants discussed the different options for action that could be discussed and explored in chapter 5, as described in the following sections.

3.7.1 Barriers to implementation and creating an enabling environment

Participants recommended that a key role of the chapter could be to **analyse barriers to the implementation of policies and actions** that support biodiversity and Indigenous Peoples and local communities, noting that a great deal of information on options for action, roles and

responsibilities has already been published, including by IPBES, but implementation often remains lacking.

Participants noted that part of this work could include assessing **where IPBES assessments and other global or regional processes, agreements or protocols have made an impact** in terms of support for biocultural systems and rights, particularly at national and local levels, and exploring the mechanisms and policy frameworks that have supported these impacts (including holistic policy frameworks that break down traditional policy silos). Options for action and ways forward could be proposed based on this work.

3.7.2 Working across scales

3.7.2.1 Analysis of connections through local, national and global levels

Participants recommended that the assessment **analyses connections across local, national and global scales**, including between the CBD, KMGBF, NBSAPs and other national and local processes. The chapter could analyse the ways in which processes, participation and governance are connected at different scales and the ways that these connections have supported positive impacts for Indigenous Peoples, local communities and biodiversity, or where this has not been achieved. Participants highlighted that often action and coherence at national scales seems to be lacking, which creates a barrier between local and global scales.

As noted above, participants emphasized that it would be important to **highlight examples or successful mechanisms and policy frameworks** that have supported positive impacts, including connections through different scales. This could include analysis of connections between monitoring and reporting systems at different levels. At the global level, this could include *Indigenous Navigator*, the *Local Biodiversity Outlooks*, CBD, KMGBF and other mechanisms including the work of *Subsidiary Body on Article 8(j) - Traditional Knowledge, Innovations and Practices*, and its traditional knowledge indicators. At the national level it could include NBSAPs and other processes where ILK or Indigenous and local community participation are being coordinated at national scales, for example the Philippines Indigenous Peoples Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (IPBSAP – see the example in section 3.5.3.3 above) and at the local level, community-based monitoring and information systems and customary governance institutions. Participants noted that there is hope among Indigenous Peoples and local communities that their contributions can be recognized, accounted for, supported and compensated via the KMGBF, but it remains unclear how this can occur, especially if there is a disconnect at national levels between local actions and contributions and global processes.

3.7.2.2 Scaling of ILK and contributions from Indigenous Peoples and local communities

Participants noted that the second global assessment (and chapter 5 in particular, working with chapters 2 and 3) could be an opportunity to build on the first global assessment, which demonstrated that while the contributions to biodiversity and wellbeing by Indigenous Peoples

and local communities often take place at local levels, they are **regionally and globally significant** when aggregated beyond local scales. This finding of the first global assessment helped to change generally held opinions that Indigenous Peoples and local communities and their knowledge were only relevant or significant in local, isolated cases.

Participants highlighted that it could also be important to explore the ways in which **Indigenous Peoples and local communities are building connections among themselves** to enhance their impact and significance at other scales, including through work at international levels around advocacy and encouraging shifts in values.

Participants also explained that **Indigenous governance already spans different scales**, from local to national, or covering vast territories, like Nunavut. Analyzing the processes, impacts and enabling factors for success of cross-scale Indigenous governance could be an important contribution of the assessment.

3.7.3 Respect for rights

3.7.3.1 *Indigenous rights, biocultural rights and applicable rights of local communities*

Participants emphasized that respect for rights should be a key foundation for the chapter, including respect for **Indigenous rights, biocultural rights and community rights, as well as other applicable rights of local communities**. Chapter 5 could build on the work of previous chapters to explore the impacts of past violations of rights, including harassment and killings of environmental and Indigenous defenders, forced displacements and developments proceeding without FPIC. It could also explore examples and contexts where Indigenous rights, biocultural rights and other applicable rights of local communities have been upheld. This could include, for example, FPIC, land tenure, the protection of the interrelations between communities and lands and waters. The positive impacts of respect for rights, on communities and biodiversity, could be assessed, as well as policy frameworks and mechanisms that support or hinder respect for rights, and ways forward.

3.7.3.2 *Responsibilities and relationships*

Participants noted that, often, Indigenous Peoples aim to leverage their rights to **assert their responsibilities and relationships** towards other aspects of nature and nonhuman relatives.

Example

Anishinaabeg communities in the United States have retained rights via the 1836 Treaty of Washington, as affirmed in United States courts, and they use this as a mechanism for maintaining ways of life and asserting responsibilities to nonhuman relatives across jurisdictions, including on federal and state lands and waters.

3.7.3.3 Justice

Some participants also noted that while rights are important, they are not the end goal, and they will evolve as, or if, conditions improve **towards justice**. Rights are needed for recognition, reclamation and revitalisation, but the evolving end goal is transformation of relationships with each other and the natural world, enacted through responsibility. Justice could therefore be an important theme to explore, including intergenerational justice.¹⁹

3.7.3.4 Rights of nature

Participants noted that the chapter could also explore other forms or expressions of rights, including **rights of nature**, and how these can support or harm the rights and aspirations of Indigenous Peoples and local communities. Participants noted that the recognition of rights of nature can advance environmental protection, but they can also conflict with Indigenous rights. However, in other cases, Indigenous Peoples have themselves proposed such mechanisms to recognise the agency and personhood of non-human beings.

Examples

Colombia's Supreme Court granted legal personhood to the Amazon in 2018, but this ruling did not account for the collective rights of Indigenous Peoples who hold collective title over 50% of the Amazonian territory.

The Whanganui River in **New Zealand** has been recognized as having legal personhood, and therefore the same rights as a person, after advocacy by Māori groups.

3.7.3.5 Biocultural rights

Participants highlighted that the assessment could also explore other innovative frameworks, such as **biocultural rights** which aim to protect the sacred balance and harmony of Indigenous Peoples within nature. These types of rights could protect the interactions between people and other elements of nature, recognizing livelihoods and the ways in which different groups use landscapes, for example the way that Saami herders use landscapes on seasonal cycles that can change from year to year.

3.7.4 Self-determination and governance

3.7.4.1 Supporting self-determination and community jurisdiction of lands and waters

Participants emphasized that many communities seek **self-determination** and jurisdiction over their lands, waters and communities, through their customary governance mechanisms or other governance processes (rather than only entering into co-management), as discussed in the sections above. This builds on the growing recognition that Indigenous Peoples and local

¹⁹ See: [Reimagining the Human Environment Relationship: Indigenous Philosophy and Intergenerational Justice](#)

communities have often been highly effective at governing and managing biodiversity and human-wellbeing, but that often external governance regimes hinder their efforts to make and implement decisions on their lands and waters.

Participants recommended that the chapter could **explore examples of Indigenous self-governance** and their impacts on biodiversity and community wellbeing. This could include exploration and analysis of the policy frameworks and mechanisms that support or hinder this, and ways forward. This could include examples from Colombia, Canada and Rapa Nui, Chile.

Example

After years of reclamation and negotiation, the government of **Colombia** recognized Indigenous Peoples as Environmental Authorities. The assessment could explore the enabling policy framework and conditions, what this recognition means in practice, how Indigenous authorities are responding, and the likely impacts at local levels on biocultural governance.

Participants also highlighted that Indigenous customary governance may be functioning within **different types of legal and official recognition**, for example sole jurisdiction, land ownership, reserved, co-management, or with no recognized status or tenure. These different legal situations and their impacts on customary governance could be explored.

Participants highlighted that exploring **leadership by women**, and ways to better recognize and support this would be important.

The role and effectiveness of **biocultural community protocols**, based on customary governance and aiming to establish rules by which external actors can engage with communities, could also be examined. The role of customary governance in mediating conflicts could also be explored.

Participants noted that **social movements and other alliances** between Indigenous Peoples and local communities and other groups, and their impacts, could also be explored.

3.7.4.2 Indigenous and local community leadership and participation in governance

Participants noted that it will also be important to explore the extent to which Indigenous Peoples and local communities can **participate in governance and policymaking at different levels**, particularly local to national. This could include analysis of the impacts of different governance models on biodiversity and community wellbeing, as well as policy frameworks and mechanisms that support or hinder this, and ways forward.

Co-management arrangements could also be explored, noting that often these do not function well in reality, so the chapter could aim to determine the principles and processes that lead to more successful outcomes, for example control by customary governance systems, FPIC and others.

3.7.5 Culture and education

3.7.5.1 Supporting continuity, revitalization and resurgence of knowledge and culture

Participants noted that, building on previous chapters, chapter 5 could explore the policy contexts and mechanisms that can **support biocultural revitalization and resurgence and knowledge transmission**, exploring cases where communities are revitalizing their knowledge systems, languages, food systems, practices, rituals and values systems, alongside restoring their lands and waters, and the impacts of these processes, and how they can be supported going forward.

Participants noted that **ILK systems often receive less respect and recognition** than “mainstream” science, and available funding and resources often reflect this. For example, traditional healers usually receive far less support than “mainstream” medical practitioners.

Participants highlight that **revitalizing food systems** is particularly important for many Indigenous Peoples and local communities, as food systems combine knowledge, culture, identity, livelihoods, lands, waters, spirituality and wellbeing. Participants highlighted that Indigenous food systems do not only include only how food is grown and produced, but also how it is sold and prepared, and the knowledge, cultural identity, community memory and governance associated with the entire system. Food systems can also include traditional medicines and even cosmetics. A broad, holistic vision of food systems is therefore needed. Many efforts around the world, for example in the Philippines, Peru and Canada, aim to restore traditional crops and the practices and spiritual connections associated with them. This can include efforts to reengage youth in traditional hunting, gathering or agricultural practices. Participants noted however that in some cases, efforts to revitalize traditional crops are hindered by a lack of access for communities to seed banks, botanical collections and other repositories of species that are no longer present locally. Facilitating access would support communities in reinstating traditional diets.

Participants noted that revitalization may be particularly difficult **where communities have moved to urban settings**, or have experienced other ruptures with their lands and waters. They also noted that many “urban” communities do maintain relationships with ancestral lands and waters, but this is not always the case. Most urban spaces were not created to enhance Indigenous Peoples’ quality of life. Analysing strategies for biocultural revitalization in urban context could therefore be an important contribution from the assessment.

Loss of languages was also highlighted by participants as a significant threat to the cultures and knowledge systems of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, which can be very difficult to counter given the pressures of “mainstream” society and education systems. Exploring strategies, success stories and enabling conditions could therefore be important.

Examples

In **Canada**, Caldwell First Nation hosted a day of field and community visits during the workshop. They explained that they were greatly impacted by colonial pressures, including losing their original Anishnaabe name for their community. They were also forcibly removed from the Point Pelee National Park, a spit of forested land that runs into Lake Erie. The information and tourist information relating to the park was subsequently told from the point of view of the settlers. The First Nation are now working with Parks Canada (the national park service) to restore cultural connections to the park, including creating ceremonial and gathering spaces within the park, and retelling the history and biodiversity of the park from the perspective of the First Nations communities who lived there and who continue to maintain connection with it. This demonstrates how biocultural relations can be restored. It also demonstrates that respect for Indigenous rights does not need to be in conflict with protected areas.

In **Uganda**, a programme brings youth from different communities together, to discuss the causes of inter-community conflicts, and to learn methods of dialogue and conflict resolution as well as resource-sharing.

In **Nigeria**, the COVID-19 pandemic and other health crises have helped to demonstrate the importance of working with traditional systems of medicine, and this has created new awareness in the government about the importance of ILK systems and attention to local contexts. Traditional midwifery is also receiving more recognition, as it is seen to be providing much needed support to women in communities, including around traditional obstetric practices utilization of animal placentas during dystocia.²⁰ In some cases, traditional practices are being supplemented by information from science, for example about the transmission of HIV, which supports traditional healers in their work.²¹ There is also increasing awareness that ILK supports food systems and environmental protection.²²

²⁰ See: Onuaguluchi G. and Ghasi S. (1996) The pharmacological basis for the use of dried sheep placenta in traditional obstetric practice in Nigeria, *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, Volume 54, Issue 1, ISSN 0378-8741. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0378874196014456>

²¹ See: Ondwela M., Mothiba T., Mangi N. and Ter Goon D. (2019) "I Visited a Traditional Healer Because I Felt I wasn't Getting any Better by Using Active Antiretroviral". Understanding Cultural Imperatives in the Context of Adherence to Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy. *Open Public Health Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2174/1874944501912010315>

²² See:

- Osunderu, O. A. (2024) Utilization of African Giant Snail by Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) in S/W Nigeria. Book of Conference Proceedings, 27th August 2024. Publisher: *Society for Medicinal Plants and Economic Development (SOMPED)*.

3.7.5.2 Exploring and supporting diverse modes of education

Participants highlighted that many Indigenous Peoples and local communities see **imposed education systems as inappropriate** for their communities and youth, noting that these imposed systems can instil different knowledge, values and aspirations in their young people, as well as undermining the authority of knowledge holders in their communities. Overall, this can create cultural disruption and often does not prepare their youth for the real-world practical context of living in a community.

Participants explained that many communities recognize that some formal education is needed, but they often want to develop **mixed education approaches** that include ILK systems and methods or practices, time spent on the land with elders, or other mechanisms. This can also apply to adult education, for example, training community members as Indigenous forest guards, traditional midwives or healers.

Indigenous languages are often a key consideration within Indigenous education systems, recognizing that formal education, which is often taught in non-Indigenous languages, can be one of the greatest influences on language decline. Meanwhile, teaching in Indigenous and local languages can be an important pathway to revitalizing languages, and knowledge and culture.

Examples

A participant shared the example from the Cauca region of **Colombia**, where, following gaining control of their lands, Indigenous groups decided that they needed to create an Indigenous university where teachers knew the Indigenous language and values. Part of this effort has also included women-led efforts to teach midwifery and healing.

In some First Nations communities in **Canada**, women from the communities have become leaders within the schools, to ensure that they teach Indigenous languages, knowledge and values, as well as ceremonies and other culturally important activities. They recognize this as an important step towards decolonization.

The assessment could explore and assess these types of programmes, their impacts on biodiversity and community wellbeing, as well as policy frameworks and mechanisms that support or hinder Indigenous education, and ways forward.

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- Owumi, B. E., 1998. "Traditional Practitioners (Healers and Healing Practices)", (Pp. 223-233) in E. A. Oke and B. E. Owumi (eds.), Reading in Medical Sociology. Ibadan: Resource Development and Management Services (RDMS).

3.7.5.3 Supporting policymakers and researchers in understanding and giving validity to diverse forms of knowledge

As discussed above, participants also noted that the assessment could play an important role in **demonstrating what evidence can look like**, including storytelling, rituals and other expressions. It will also be important to demonstrate how ILK can be validated within ILK systems themselves, rather than by external researchers or knowledge systems.

Participants noted that the assessment could also demonstrate to policymakers **how to work with different knowledge systems within decision-making**. Existing mechanisms and processes at different levels could also be assessed and presented, and ways forward.

3.7.6 Economic development and funding

3.7.6.1 Exploring and supporting diverse models of economic development

Participants explained that many communities are exploring **diverse ways of ensuring their economic viability and sustainability**, while also supporting community values, knowledge systems, intergenerational health and wellbeing, self-determination, governance and sustainable use of resources. Often, this involves looking to the values that existed before colonialism. These enterprises are often based around traditional foods, medicines or cosmetics, and centre community wellbeing and sustainability over individual profit. Examples include cooperatives in Borneo and community enterprises in northern Thailand.

Such community enterprises may also have an explicit aim of **creating opportunities for knowledge transmission**.

Examples

In northern **Thailand**, community enterprises have created opportunities for youth to be engaged on the land with elders and other knowledge holders.

In **the Philippines**, the development of community cooperatives enhanced the economic strength of some communities, and as a result, they were able to create television and radio stations that support knowledge transmission and cultural continuity.

Participants noted that these modes of economic development not only provide locally culturally appropriate and sustainable solutions, but can also provide **models for larger scale re-evaluations of the values and worldviews** that underpin “mainstream” business and global economies, moving away from individual profit and towards biocultural wellbeing.

Participants also noted that there is potential for **tourism** to support communities to protect their lands and waters in ways that also support them economically, if they are managed well and if communities have decision-making control over how such businesses develop.

3.7.6.2 Access and benefit sharing and payments for contributions

Participants highlighted that it would be important to assess and monitor the different mechanisms that may (or may not) be in place to **compensate and pay Indigenous Peoples and local communities for their contributions to conservation or to marketable products**. This could include, for example, payments for protecting biodiversity, watersheds or carbon sequestering forests, and access and benefit sharing agreements for products such as Rooibos tea. The Cali Fund (which aims to be an enabling financial engine of the KMGBF for the fair and equitable sharing of benefits from the use of digital sequence information on genetic resources) could be explored as an example. Other legal frameworks, such as the Nagoya Protocol to the CBD, and the World Intellectual Property Organization Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Associated Traditional Knowledge, could also be explored for their successes and weaknesses.

Participants noted that, in spite of these mechanisms, **equitable and fair distribution of benefits to Indigenous Peoples is still not guaranteed** when their knowledge is accessed and used in product development. Existing mechanisms and processes at different levels could therefore be assessed and presented, along with ways forward, potentially including conservation and restoration payments.

Participants noted that it is also important to analyse the ways that **some programmes of funds or payments may not be culturally appropriate** and may promote different value systems for communities, or create further inequalities. Some financial schemes, such as biodiversity or carbon credits, may also incentivise governments to remove people from their lands or have other negative effects. These could also be analysed and presented, along with safeguards and ways in which they could be adjusted to ensure they benefit and compensate Indigenous Peoples and local communities, rather than causing harm.

3.7.6.3 Access to funding

Participants highlighted that many Indigenous Peoples and local communities currently **struggle to gain access to funding**. Funding to support communities is often instead directed to governments or large NGOs, and often little trickles down to the community level. Innovative mechanisms may be needed to ensure direct access to funding for communities, including simplified processes for applying for funds and reporting on outcomes.

Participants noted that many communities have ideas, or small-scale activities, which aim to reconnect youth to ILK systems, or enhance traditional healing, or ecological restoration, but they often **lack the funds to scale these up** through their communities and lands. Giving proper recognition and respect to ILK systems would be a first step to ensuring that appropriate funding is given to support these systems in modern community settings.

Participants explained that the **Cali Fund** tied to the KMGBF, mentioned above, aims to ensure that 50% of the fund goes to Indigenous Peoples. However, it is not clear what is meant by ‘direct access’ to funding, and how this can function in practice.

Participants recommended that the assessment could explore **different funding mechanisms that already exist** at national and global levels, and assess their effectiveness and their impacts, as well as ways forward.

Example

In **Canada**, *NWT: Our Land for the Future*²³ is an Indigenous-led finance initiative that aims to support long-term, large-scale protection of lands and inland waters in the Northwest Territories. It is co-organized by more than 20 Indigenous Governments and organizations in the Northwest Territories, as well as the territorial government, Environment and Climate Change Canada and philanthropic organizations.

3.7.7 Research

Participants highlighted that many Indigenous Peoples and local communities want to see **more support for Indigenous-led research** using Indigenous methodologies rather than only a focus on co-production, which often in reality implies ILK systems being pressed into “mainstream” scientific assumptions, goals, frameworks and methods. Such support could include funding, but also institutional support and credence.

Participants noted that Indigenous research can help to **break down the silos in scientific disciplines**, as ILK systems and Indigenous methodologies are more likely to include holistic, biocultural approaches.

Participants emphasized that **training of community researchers** should be a priority so that research is not always framed, decided and carried out by external researchers, who may be unaware of community realities and knowledge systems, or who may be fulfilling institutional or personal agendas. Good examples of both Indigenous-led research and co-production could be explored in the assessment, demonstrating where these have led to the creation of new knowledge and new perspectives. Holistic research addressing biocultural systems, rather than siloed disciplinary approaches, would be beneficial.

Participants noted that the **principles for successful weaving and co-production** could also be explored, including Indigenous control, FPIC and processes to ensure data sovereignty and control, for example the CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics) and OCAP (Ownership, Control, Access, and Possession, as developed in Canada) principles and

²³ See: <https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/nature-legacy/about/project-finance-for-permanence/northwest-territories.html>

other frameworks. Institutional collaborations, for example, between communities and universities, could also be explored for lessons learnt.

Participants highlighted that attention, support and resources are also required for the **development of biocultural community protocols** that can set the guidelines and procedures for external researchers, industry and others who want to engage in research and bioprospecting in Indigenous and local community lands and waters. Training and certification may also be needed for researchers who wish to work with ILK systems and communities.

Examples

In the **United States of America**, there is a project on revitalising ancestral seeds, where a formally trained botanist and a council of Indigenous elders are working together to decide on the goals, questions and methods. These types of projects can offer important examples of how co-production, or weaving or braiding of knowledge systems, can be carried out in practice, where there is strong Indigenous leadership in the project. The U.S. National Science Foundation Center for Braiding Indigenous Knowledges and Science (NSF CBIKS) may be a good source of examples and methods.²⁴

In **Canada**, data from “mainstream” science on health and wellbeing was shared with community elders, to ask them what should be done based on the findings. In this way, control over the response to the findings was given to the customary governance system of the community. Based on this, the elders and community decided to reintroduce “rites of passage” for children, which include learning traditional ways of knowing their bodies and behaviour towards sexuality. Studies are now needed with the community in order to monitor and document outcomes of these processes.

3.7.8 Values and concepts

Participants noted that previous chapters could include an analysis of existing societal concepts and values and their impacts. This could lead, in chapter 5, to exploration of options for actions to bring about **change in broader societal values**. This change could aim to enhance appreciation and understanding of biocultural systems rather than, on one hand, concepts of pristine nature untouched by humans, and on the other, unsustainable economic development.

3.7.9 Protecting and restoring lands and waters

3.7.9.1 Legal protection of lands and waters

Participants noted that **stronger legal safeguards and protections** are essential to sustain healthy lands and waters, which are essential for the identities, livelihoods, food systems and cultures of

²⁴ See: <https://www.umass.edu/gateway/research/indigenous-knowledges>

many Indigenous Peoples and local communities. Such safeguards and protection should include recognition of and support for customary governance systems. In many areas, restoration may be needed to restore the health and vitality of ecosystems. Landscape approaches are also important for maintaining and restoring diverse ecosystems and livelihoods. Such efforts should also include cultural revitalization, resurgence or continuity, recognizing that both culture and ecosystems are part of holistic biocultural systems.

Participants also noted that, in the past, their lands and waters were often considered to be poor or lacking value, or Indigenous Peoples and local communities were deliberately moved onto lands that were perceived not to be of value to governments. However, increasingly, **Indigenous and local community lands are recognized as valuable areas for nature and culture**, which provides potential benefits and also risks for the communities who live within or use those lands and waters.

Overall, participants cautioned that **protection and restoration of nature should not take place at the expense of human wellbeing**, for example through evictions of people from protected areas, or by ignoring increasing cases of human-wildlife conflict caused by increases in large carnivores and other species, which can occur around some protected areas.

3.7.9.2 Regulation and oversight of business and industry

Participants noted that in many cases, Indigenous Peoples and local communities are caring for their lands and waters, but they face significant challenges when **business and industry carry out destructive or polluting activities**. These impacts are exacerbated when governments do not hold those industries to account or enforce restoration and cleanup.

Participants also noted that, in some cases, **businesses offer communities misleading solutions or promises of benefits** from industrial development. Communities may believe them, and be led into destructive activities. More oversight of business relationships with communities may therefore be needed, including to ensure that true and reliable information is shared as part of FPIC. Capacity-building for communities may also be needed, so that they can understand their rights and the likely environmental and social impacts of industrial developments on their lands and waters.

3.7.10 Options for action by Indigenous Peoples and local communities

Participants noted that Indigenous Peoples and local communities may have options for action, depending on their contexts and political situations, including supporting and advocating for many of the transformations and options for action discussed above. This includes **upholding rights and responsibilities**, especially where communities are regaining control of their lands. The value systems and worldviews of many Indigenous Peoples and local communities encode a series of responsibilities towards people and nature, but in some cases these have been eroded

by outside pressures. Some communities may therefore see a need to refocus on their Indigenous values and responsibilities, as this will be important once they gain more control over their lands, lives, economies and education systems (for example in Canada).

Participants also noted that there is a growing opportunity for **Indigenous leadership at international levels**, for example around the CBD and its new subsidiary body for Article 8(j) of the Convention.

Exchange programmes, where communities from across countries or across the world come to together to share experiences and build capacity, are another way in which Indigenous Peoples and local communities can be supporting each other and their capacities to achieve their goals and aspirations.

4 Next steps

The following next steps follow the workshop:

- A brief initial report from the workshop was developed and shared with all assessment authors prior to their first author meeting, in Paris, France, from 24 to 28 November 2025. The results of the workshop were also presented and discussed with all authors, and particularly the chapter 2 author team and the ILK liaison group for the assessment;
- Building on the brief initial report, a full workshop report was developed from the dialogue workshop (this report), which was sent to all participants for them to edit, make additions and approve prior to finalization and publication online;
- Following the first author meeting, and using the report as a resource, the authors began to develop the draft chapters of the assessment;
- Author teams may reach out to workshop participants and other members of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, to invite them to be contributing authors;
- The first drafts of the chapters will be available for external review from 15 June to 7 August 2026, and all participants will be invited to review the drafts;
- A dialogue workshop will be organized during the review period, to enhance the participation of Indigenous Peoples and local communities in reviewing the drafts;
- A second review period for the assessment chapters and draft summary for policymakers, and a dialogue workshop, will take place in mid 2027;
- The assessment will be considered and approved at the IPBES Plenary in 2028; and
- Materials and outreach activities for Indigenous peoples and local communities based on the finalised assessment will commence follow the plenary.

Annexes

Annex 1: Agenda

Monday 3 November	
9.00am-12.30pm	Block 1: Participant Relationship Building
9.00am-9.30am	Registration
9.30am-10.30am	<p>Opening Ceremonies/ Introduction to the Land and Waters (Facilitator: Catherine Febria)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elder Dr Myrna Kicknosway, opening prayer • Abraham Francis, Thanksgiving Address • University of Windsor leadership, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Prof Clint Jacobs, Walpole Island First Nation & University of Windsor Advisor to President's office on Indigenous Initiatives ○ Dr. Shanthi Johnson, UWindsor VP Research & Innovation • Kyle Whyte, IPBES ILK task force • Lu Zhi, co-chair, Second global assessment
10.30am-10.45am	Refreshment break
10.45am-12.30pm	<p>A welcoming and cosy plenary session and small group sessions (Facilitator: Kyle Whyte)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing names and background, show and tell of a meaningful item (an object, photo, or their gift for later in the week) • Discuss: How do people express humor where you're from?
12.30pm-2.00pm	Lunch
2.00pm-4.30pm	Afternoon Block 2: ILK Methods Workshop (Objective 1-1) <i>Objective 1-1: To explore the methodologies through which Indigenous and local knowledge is currently represented in assessments, and the modes of participation for Indigenous Peoples and local communities (including the review of ILK in IPBES that was completed in 2023 and extended in 2024).</i>
2.00pm-3.15pm	<p>Plenary Information Sharing (Facilitators: Catherine Febria and Kyle Whyte)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of IPBES and current ILK methods (10 mins) • Introduction to the Network of the Centres of Distinction on Indigenous and local knowledge and the International Indigenous Forum on Biodiversity and ecosystems Services • Overview and summary of the 2023-24 reviews of ILK in IPBES • ILK experiences from the previous IPBES assessments (including from COD-ILK members and others with IPBES related projects), focusing on their meaningfulness for Indigenous Peoples and local communities: successes/ challenges/ lessons learned? • ILK experiences from other multi-lateral assessments/ processes and connections to IPBES
3.15pm-3.30pm	Refreshment break
3.30pm-4.30pm	<p>Small Group Activity for generating notes + ideas (Facilitator: Kyle Whyte)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introductions: each participant's involvement in IPBES and other assessments regarding ILK policies and practices. • What impacts has IPBES had on Indigenous peoples and Local communities?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are key successes, challenges, and lessons learned from the presentations or from each participant's own experiences?
4.30pm	Wrap up of the day
4.30pm	Optional sunset walk at Ojibway Prairie with Indigenous Youth & City of Windsor guides from Windsor's National Urban Park
6.30pm	Dinner/ spending time together

Tuesday 4 November	
9.00am-12.30pm	Morning Block 3: ILK Methods Workshop (Objectives 1-1 and 1-2) <i>Objective 1-2: To explore methodologies to further enhance the ways in which Indigenous and local knowledge can be reflected in IPBES assessments.</i>
9.00am-10.30am	Plenary Session (Facilitator: Kyle Whyte) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing discussion takeaways from Small Group Activities on Monday afternoon (focusing on lessons learned) • Open Time if there are individuals who seek to more spontaneously present
10.15am-10.30am	Refreshment break
10.30am-11.30pm	Plenary (Facilitator: Kyle Whyte) Examples from Indigenous-led, national, regional, or bi-/tri-lateral assessments and scientific processes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launching Indigenous Science in ECCC (10 minutes) (Myrle Ballard) • Status of Tribes and Climate Change Report, U.S. National Climate Assessment, and Continental Climate and Biodiversity Assessment (10 minutes) (Kyle Whyte)
11.30am-11.45am	Refreshment break
11.45am-12.30pm	Plenary Discussion (facilitator: Catherine Febria) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can we learn from participants' experiences and case studies about how to further enhance Indigenous and local knowledge in IPBES?
12.30pm-2.00pm	Lunch and first Indigenous Caucus
2.00pm-6.00pm	Afternoon Block 4: ILK Methods Workshop (Objectives 1-2 and 1-3) <i>Objective 1-3: To explore approaches to enhance the implementation of the participatory mechanism for Indigenous Peoples and local communities in IPBES assessments.</i>
2.00pm-3.45pm	Small Group Activity (Facilitator: Mariaelena Huambachano) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small group discussion of what actions and innovations should occur: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ For enhancing participation of Indigenous and local partners in IPBES processes (incl. assessments, uptake, stakeholder engagement) • Discussion of how actions and interventions can be scaled and replicated: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ For IPBES in general or specific parts of IPBES ○ Or with a particular relevance to the second global assessment
3.45pm-4.00pm	Refreshment break
3.30pm-5.00pm	Plenary Session (Facilitator: Mariaelena Huambachano): Sharing takeaways from the Small Group Activity
5.00pm-5.30pm	Plenary: Wrap-up for the day <u>Methods group</u> will work to summarize methods discussion for the joint session on Friday
6.00pm	Dinner/ Walk/ Cultural activity: Optional sunset walk at Ojibway Prairie with Indigenous Youth & City of Windsor guides from Windsor's National Urban Park

Wednesday 5 November	
9.00am-12.30pm	Morning Block 5: Introducing the second global assessment, focus on chapters 1 and 2
9.00am-10.00am	<p>Plenary presentations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome / Introduction to the second global assessment and potential outcomes to support policy development and recognition of Indigenous Peoples and local communities in policy (Lu Zhi) Lessons/findings from the first global assessment and subsequent assessments (speaker TBC) Key messages from the 2024 'Report of the Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop for the scoping of the second IPBES global assessment' (Mariaelena Huambachano)
10.00am-10.45am	<p>Plenary discussion: the second global assessment (Facilitator: Lu Zhi)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Q&A First thoughts: What are the key themes that the assessment should explore? First thoughts: What are the opportunities, risks and benefits of the assessment from the perspectives of Indigenous Peoples and local communities?
10.45am-11.00am	Refreshment break
11.00am-12.30am	<p>Plenary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brief introduction to chapter 1 Brief introduction to chapter 2 Case study (5 mins) <p>Discussion: key ILK themes, case studies and methods for chapter 2</p>
12.30pm-2.00pm	Lunch
2.00pm-6.00pm	Afternoon Block 6: the second global assessment, focus on chapters 3 and 4
2.00pm-3.30pm	<p>Plenary:</p> <p>Chapter 3: Status and Trends</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brief introduction to chapter 3 and its subchapters Case study (5 mins) <p>Discussion: key ILK themes, case studies and methods for chapter 3</p>
3.30pm-3.45pm	Refreshment break
3.45pm-5.00pm	<p>Plenary: Chapter 4: Future Pathways</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brief introduction to chapter 4 Reflections on outcomes from the IPBES workshop on scenarios and ILK (May 2025, the Philippines) Discussion: key ILK themes, case studies and methods for chapter 4
5.00pm-5.55pm	<p>Welcome to Territory Address from Chief Nikki van Oirschot, Caldwell First Nation</p> <p>Introduction to the Community Visit: background, rules, rituals, etc.</p>
5.55pm-6.00pm	Wrap-up for the day
6.30pm	Dinner/ Walk/ Cultural activity: Optional sunset walk at Ojibway Prairie with Indigenous Youth & City of Windsor guides from Windsor's National Urban Park

Thursday 6 November	
8.00am-5.00pm	Block 7: Community, lands and waters visit day
8.00am-5.00pm	Community Trip - Caldwell First Nation ecosystem restoration property <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water ceremony at newly created wetland Community Trip - Point Pelee National Park <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lunch with Indigenous Guardians from across the traditional territory (plus presentation)

Friday 7 November	
9.00am-12.30pm	Morning Block 8: the second global assessment, chapter 5 and key messages
9.00am-9.45am	Plenary Session: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflections on the previous day, planning for the day • Sharing reflections, take-away messages and inspiration from the community visit and relevance to our workshop • Wishes for our last day together in Windsor
9.45am-10.30am	Plenary: Chapter 5 - Policy Options <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief introduction to chapter 5 Discussion: key ILK themes, case studies and methods for chapter 5
10.30am-10.45am	Refreshment break
10.45am-11.45pm	Discussion continued: key ILK themes, case studies and methods for chapter 5
11.45pm-12.30pm	Plenary <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflections: What are the key themes that the assessment can explore? • Reflections: What are the opportunities, risks, and benefits of the assessment from the perspectives of Indigenous Peoples and local communities?
12.30pm-1.30pm	Lunch
1.30pm-4.30pm	Afternoon Block 9: Indigenous caucus, key messages and closing
1.30pm-2.15pm	Second Indigenous Caucus
2.15pm-2.30pm	Plenary: Report back from the Indigenous caucus
2.30pm-3.30pm	Plenary: Summarizing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key messages to consider for the second global assessment (and the first author meeting in Paris) • Key messages on methods
3.30pm-3.45pm	Plenary: Next steps
3.45pm-4.15pm	Plenary: Giveaway
4.15pm-4.30pm	Plenary: Closing and thanksgiving Address (Abraham Francis)
5.00pm	Optional sunset walk at Ojibway Prairie with Indigenous Youth & City of Windsor guides from Windsor's National Urban Park

Annex 2: FPIC document

Free, Prior and Informed Consent

The individuals whose names are listed at the end of this document agreed during the dialogue workshop to follow the principles and steps laid out in this document.

Background

Within the framework of the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP), principles of Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC) apply to research or knowledge-related interactions between Indigenous Peoples and outsiders (including researchers, scientists, journalists). Given that the dialogue process includes discussion of Indigenous and local knowledge of biodiversity and ecosystems, there may be information which the knowledge holders or their organizations or respective communities consider sensitive, private, or holding value for themselves which they do not want to share in the public domain through publications or other media without formal consent.

Principles

The dialogue will be built on equal sharing and joint learning across knowledge systems and cultures. The aim is to create an environment where people feel comfortable and able to speak on equal terms, which is an important precondition for true dialogue.

To achieve these aims, the following goals are emphasized:

- Equality of all participants and absence of coercive influence
- Listening with empathy and seeking to understand each other's viewpoints
- Accurate and empathetic communication
- Bringing assumptions into the open

If participants feel that the above goals are not being achieved at any point during IPBES activities, participants are asked to bring this to the attention of the organizers of the activity, or the IPBES technical support unit on ILK, at: ilk.tsu.ipbes@unesco.org.

Sharing knowledge and respecting FPIC

To ensure that knowledge is shared in appropriate ways during dialogue workshops and other IPBES activities, and that information and materials produced after these activities are used in ways that respect FPIC, the following was put forward:

1. Guardianship – participants who represent organizations and communities

- Principles of guardianship will be discussed with participants from Indigenous Peoples and local communities at the beginning of IPBES activities.
- Participants who represent organizations or communities will act as the guardians of the use of the knowledge and materials from their respective organizations or communities that is shared before, during or after the workshop. Any use of their organizations' or communities' knowledge will be discussed and approved by the guardians, as legitimate representatives of their organizations or communities. Guardians are expected to contact their respective organizations and communities when they need advice. Guardians are also expected to seek consent from their organizations or communities when they consider that this is required, keeping in mind that sharing details of their community's knowledge can potentially have negative consequences, for example sharing the locations and uses of medicinal plants.

2. FPIC rights during dialogue workshops and other activities

- The FPIC rights of the Indigenous Peoples participating in dialogue workshops or other activities will be discussed prior to the beginning of the activity, until participants feel comfortable and well informed about their rights and the process, including the eventual planned use and distribution of information. This discussion may be revisited during the activity, and will be revisited at the end of dialogue workshops once participants have engaged in the dialogue process.
- Participants do not have to answer any questions that they do not want to answer, and do not need to participate in any part of an activity in which they do not wish to participate.
- At any point, any participant can decide that they do not want particular information to be documented or shared outside of the activity. Participants will inform organizers and other participants of this. Organizers and participants will ensure that the information is not recorded. Participants can also request that the information is only recorded as a general statement attributed to a region or country, rather than to a specific community.
- Permission for photographs must be agreed prior to photos being taken and participants have the right not to be photographed. Organizers will take note of this.

3. After the activity

- Permission will be obtained before any photograph of a participant is used or distributed in any form.
- Permission will be obtained before any list of participants is used or distributed in any form.

- Participants maintain intellectual property rights over all information collected from them about themselves or their communities, including photographs. Their intellectual property rights should be protected, pursuant to applicable laws.
- Copies of all information collected will be provided to the participants for approval.
- The information collected during the activity will not be used by IPBES for any purposes other than those for which consent has been granted, unless permission is sought and given by participants. Participants note that IPBES does not have control over how others may use its publicly available materials that may contain ILK.
- Participants can decline to consent or withdraw their knowledge or information from the process at any time, and records of that information will be deleted if requested by the participant. Participants should however be aware that once an assessment is published it cannot be changed, and information incorporated into the assessment cannot therefore be withdrawn from the assessment after this point.
- Participants have the opportunity of reviewing and commenting upon the final product during the draft review period, and a dialogue workshop will be organized to support this, bearing in mind that responsibility for the final product rests exclusively with the authors.

Annex 3: Participants of the dialogue workshop

Name	Country	Affiliation
Participants		
José ARIAS-BUSTAMANTE	Chile / Canada	Indigenous Science Policy Advisor, Environment and Climate Change Canada
Myrle BALLARD	Canada	IPBES ILK task force / University of Calgary
Allison BISHOP	Canada	University of Guelph
Evan BOWNESS	Canada / Brazil	Western University
Joji CARIÑO	The Philippines	IPBES ILK task force / Forest Peoples Programme
Robin Michigizhigookwe CLARK	USA	Independent Consultant
Q"Apaj CONDE	Bolivia	IPBES ILK task force / CBD secretariat
Alexander DUNCAN	Canada	Fellow, second global assessment / The University of British Columbia
Janessa ESQUIBLE	Canada	Great Lakes Indigenous Fisheries Postdoctoral Fellow
Catherine FEBRIA	Canada	Co-chair, IPBES ILK task force / Local Organizer / University of Windsor
Abraham FRANCIS	Canada / USA	Chiefs of Ontario
Maret J. HEATTA	Norway	Saami Council
Sherilee HARPER	Canada	Working Group I Vice Chair, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)
Guadalupe Yesenia HERNANDEZ	Mexico	IPBES ILK task force
Mariaelena HUAMBACHANO	Peru	Coordinating lead author, chapter 2, second global assessment / IPBES ILK task force / Syracuse University
Mary Beth JAGER	USA	University of Michigan School for Environment and Sustainability
Debissa LEMESSA	Ethiopia	Lead author, chapter 3, second global assessment / Addis Ababa University
Yolanda LÓPEZ MALDONADO	Mexico	Review editor, chapter 2, second global assessment / Earth System Scientist, Founder & CEO Indigenous Science
Zhi LU	China	Co-chair, second global assessment / Peking University
Gathuru MBURU	Kenya	Ngaatho Community Foundation
Shiloh MAPLES	USA	University of Michigan
Dawn MARTIN-HILL	Canada	McMaster University
Leigh MCGAUGHEY	South Africa / Canada	The River Institute
Gabriel NEMOGÁ-SOTO	Colombia / Canada	Lead author, chapter 3, second global assessment / University of Winnipeg
Oluwakemi Abosede OSUNDERU	Nigeria	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN) and Hermon Development Foundation
Loupa PIUS	Uganda	IPBES ILK task force / KAYESE Community Organisation

Maria Elena REGPALA	The Philippines	Centers of Distinction of Indigenous and Local Knowledge
Aibek SAMAKOV	Kyrgyzstan	Lead author, chapter 2, second global assessment / University of Central Asia
Polina SHULBAEVA	Russian Federation	Center of Distinction Indigenous Knowledge of the North, member of the Network COD-ILK to IPBES
Nataliya STRYAMETS	Ukraine	Lead author, chapter 3, second global assessment/ IPBES ILK task force / Researcher, Nature reserve "Roztochya"
Brenda TAHI	New Zealand	Lead author, chapter 2, second global assessment / Tūhoe Tuawhenua Trust
Krushil WATENE	New Zealand	University of Auckland
Kyle WHYTE	USA	IPBES ILK task force / Local organizer / University of Michigan
IPBES / UNESCO secretariats		
Peter BATES	UK	IPBES ILK technical support unit, UNESCO
Dorothee BAUM	Germany	Technical support unit for the second global assessment, IPBES
Sofia DELGER	Argentina	BES-Net ILK support unit, UNESCO
David GONZALEZ	Mexico	IPBES secretariat

